

**INVESTIGATION ON AIRFLOW CHARACTERISTICS
AND THERMAL COMFORT IN AN INDOOR
SWIMMING POOL**

By

Eng. Ahmed Mohamed Hanafi Mahmoud

A Thesis Submitted to the
Faculty of Engineering at Cairo University
in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree of
MASTER OF SCIENCE
in

Mechanical Power Engineering

FACULTY OF ENGINEERING, CAIRO UNIVERSITY
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Title of Thesis:

Investigation on Airflow Characteristics and Thermal Comfort in an Indoor Swimming Pool

Key Words: Indoor swimming pool, sports buildings, Computational fluid dynamics (CFD), Ventilation, Evaporation rate, thermal and humidity conditions, Thermal comfort.

Summary:

The Design of Air conditioning system in an Indoor Swimming Pool Hall plays a critical role in providing the thermal comfort and hygiene environment. This study can improve and evolve the architectural design to ensure optimum achievement of the previous goal.

This research aims to study the effect of the air curtain flows on heat and mass characteristics by calculating the velocity, temperature and moisture distribution inside the Swimming Pool.

Disclaimer

I at this moment declare that this thesis is my own original work and that no part of it has been submitted for a degree qualification at any other university or institute.

I further declare that I have appropriately acknowledged all sources used and have cited them in the references section.

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Dedication

This study is wholeheartedly dedicated to my beloved parents and my brother , who have been my source of inspiration and gave me strength when I thought of giving up, who continually provide their moral, spiritual, emotional, and financial support.

Acknowledgment

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Nomenclature

Symbol	Description
C	Constant
C_p	Constant pressure specific heat, J/kg.K
d	Distance, m
$D_{i,m}$	Diffusion coefficient for species i in mixture m , m ² /s
D	Fluid Domain
E	Total energy of a fluid particle, J Dimension Less term describing the turbulent dissipation rate, ε
\vec{F}	External body forces, N
g	Gravitational acceleration, m/s ²
G	Filter function
G_b	Generation of turbulent kinetic energy, k , due to buoyancy
G_k	Turbulence kinetic energy production
h	Enthalpy, kJ/kg
h_j^0	enthalpy of formation of species j
H	Height, m
I	Unit tensor Fluctuation intensity
\vec{J}_j	Diffusion flux of species j
k	Turbulent Kinetic energy, m ² /s ² Thermal conductivity coefficient, W/m °C
K	Dimensionless group describing the turbulent kinetic energy, k .
L_s	Mixing length, m
m	Mass, kg
p	Pressure, Pa
Pr	Prandtl Number, $Pr = C_p \mu / k$
Ra	Rayleigh number, $Ra = Gr \times Pr$
Re	Reynolds Number, $Re = \rho U l / \mu$
RH	Relative humidity, %

R_i	Net rate of production of species i
\mathfrak{R}_j	Volumetric rate of creation of species j
S	Source term modulus of the mean rate-of-strain tensor
Sc	Schmidt number, $Sc = \nu/D_{im}$
t	Time, s
T	Dry bulb Temperature of gas mixture, K
T'	Temperature fluctuation, K
\bar{u}_i	Mean velocity components, m/s
u'_i	Fluctuating velocity components. m/s
u	Instantaneous velocity component in x direction, m/s
U	Axial velocity, m/s
U_o	Inlet jet velocity, m/s
V	Computational cell Volume, m ³
\vec{v}	Velocity vector, m/s
v	Velocity magnitude, m/s Instantaneous velocity component in y direction, m/s
w	Instantaneous velocity component in z direction, m/s
Y_j	Mass fraction of species j
x, y, z	Cardinal coordinate components

Greek Letters

Symbol	Description
β	Thermal expansion coefficient, K^{-1}
Δ	Change interval of any property
δ	Delta function
ε	Turbulence dissipation rate m^2/s^3
Γ	Diffusivity, m^2/s
ρ	Density, kg/m^3
ϕ	Donates Scalar property (i.e. density, energy, ..etc.) Relative humidity, %
τ	Shear Stress, Pa
τ_{ij}	Subgrid-scale stress
τ_{ij}	Stress tensor
Ψ	Gaussian random number
∇	Gradient
μ	Dynamic viscosity, N/s^2
ν	Kinematic Viscosity, m^2/s
ω	Vorticity
κ	Von Kármán constant

Superscripts and Subscripts

Symbol	Description
--	Mean Property
-	Vector
'	Fluctuating component of any property
T	Transpose
Av	Average
<i>eff</i>	Effective property
<i>i, j, k</i>	Donates Cartesian coordinate direction takes the value of axis X,Y, Z,
<i>I</i>	Species <i>i</i>
in	inlet
<i>t</i>	Turbulent property
T	Time
<i>m</i>	Mass - mixture
<i>h</i>	Heat
crit	Critical
<i>ref</i>	Reference
<i>w</i>	Wall
	Water vapour

Abbreviations

Symbol	Description
2D	Two Dimensional configurations
3D	Three Dimensional configurations
3DHVAC	Three-dimensional HVAC program package
ACH	Air Changes per Hour
AMG	Algebraic Multigrid
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
ASA	Amateur Swimming Association
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers
ASM	Algebraic Stress Model
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DNS	Direct Numerical Simulation
EMC	Environmental Moisture Content
FINA	Federation Internationale de Natation (English: International Swimming Federation)
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air-Conditioning
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
LMA	Local Mean Age of Air, s
OpenFOAM	Open Source Field Operation And Manipulation
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
PPD	Percentage Predicted Dissatisfied
RANS	Reynolds average Navier- Stokes equations
RH	Relative Humidity
RNG	Renormalization group
RSM	Reynolds Stress Model
SIMPLE	Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations
SIMPLEC	Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure-Linked Equations Consistent
SST	Shear Stress Transport
TCO	Thermal Comfort of Their Occupants
VDI	Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (English: Association of German Engineers)
VOC	Volatile Organic Chemical
WS	Water Surface

Abstract

The design of air conditioning system in an indoor swimming pool hall plays a critical role in providing the thermal comfort and hygiene environment. This research objected to studying the effect of the air curtain flows on heat and mass transfer by investigating the velocity, temperature and moisture distribution inside the hall of the swimming pool which is occupied by many spectators and swimmers.

The study carried out using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation using a commercial CFD package, namely ANSYS Fluent 17.2. The CFD modeling techniques solved the continuity, momentum, energy, and species transport equations in addition to k-epsilon model equations for turbulence closure. Mesh element sizes used in the present work exceeded 5.6 million mesh element which allowed better and meaningful predictions of the flow regimes.

The study performed inside a semi-Olympic pool located at Bishop's University in Sherbrooke (Quebec, Canada) by drawing the geometry of roughly trapezoidal shape and dimensions of (34.5 m×25 m×8 m) by SpaceClaim 3D modeling software for six different simulation cases. The investigation included the influence of the location and number of ventilation and air conditioning supply and extracts openings at the lowest ACH (Air Changes Per Hour) recommended by ASHRAE (American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers) and evaluated by Fanger's model.

Improving thermal comfort of the occupied area around swimming pool and spectator stand area is the primary concern of this study, therefore, to achieve the adequate conditions of thermal and airflow pattern the inlet grilles concentrated in this area with different heights and shapes. The outlet grilles in configuration 1 are at the middle of the ceiling in swimming pool area and in the side walls of the spectators stand area. Also, the inlet grilles are at the height of 3m from the floor in the side walls of the swimming pool and at the back wall of the spectator area. Configuration 2 outlet grilles are located in the ceiling at spectator stand area to investigate the effect of changing outlet position. Configuration 3 the inlet grilles are changed to be in 30cm height from the floor at swimming pool area. Configuration 4 the inlet grilles in the spectator stand area changed to the fence at 30 cm. To study the effect of shape change configuration 5 used circular inlet as recommended from ASHRAE at the ceiling, configuration 6 is studied the combination of best results from configuration 1 to configuration 5 to achieve suitable thermal comfort for the hall.

The validation results show a good agreement between ANSYS Fluent 17.2 results and OpenFOAM software results. Moreover, the results of the comparisons between the 6 configurations revealed that the circular inlet in the ceiling at low-speed air supply shown better air distribution and thermal comfort in the spectators stand area than rectangle inlet. Also, the rectangle inlet in side walls in swimming pool area shows better better air distribution and thermal comfort than circular inlet at low-speed air supply due to the height of the hall, finally ACH for the water pool area and spectator stand should be different due to the number of persons per square meter

Chapter 1

Introduction

In many sports pools, not just the water territory takes up a massive part of the swimming pool, but also grandstands and seats for spectators. In addition to the swimming pool itself, it requires efficient and reliable air conditioning. If the moist air continually dehumidified, Only by that a comfortable climate for the spectators in the grandstand achieve.

The air conditioning of an indoor swimming pool hall fulfills two main tasks:

- Achieve thermal comfort and indoor air quality sportsmen and women and wellness fans.
- Protect the material of the building against damage from moisture over long the time.

Irrespective of the intensity of use of the swimming pool hall, the high level of water evaporation requires 24-hour operation of the air conditioning system, ideally regulated by an intelligently designed and controlled system. Indoor swimming pool air conditioning is a complicated system.

The air-conditioning technology must also be of an appropriate size to guarantee a consistently good climate. The higher the volume, the more important is the efficiency of the fan motors are used. The operating cost factor plays a vital role in sports pools, as the operators of the facility are usually local authorities or the state. The modernization of obsolescent air-conditioning technology often offers a considerable reduction in operating costs. New buildings which are planned and constructed from the beginning in line with passive building criteria, for example, can achieve energy savings of well over 50% compared to standard designs [1]. In the planning of a sports swimming pool, future demands should also consider at the planning stage.

1.1 Energy Use in Swimming Pools

Indoor swimming pools consume more energy than sports halls and outdoor pools because of the higher latent, sensible and ventilation loads, due to the evaporation of the pool water. The evaporation of the pool water leads to high latent heat losses, increasing the load for water heating to avoid the cooling effect. Furthermore, the indoor humidity levels increased, and more energy must consume for heating the makeup air in exchange for increasing the ventilation rates to reach the required temperature and avoid condensation on the surfaces of the walls, window, and roof.

1.2 Classification of Swimming Pools

Swimming pool facilities consist one of the preferable types of sports facilities since it provides many activities. For example, many health clubs dispose of swimming pools for exercise or relaxation. Many universities have swimming pools facilities for recreation or competitive training of swimming teams. Moreover, numerous cities and

towns make available for use public pools. In Australia for example, it is common to meet swimming pools in each large town or city, as citizens are motivated to use them not only for their pleasure but also to develop their physical activities. So, swimming pools can found in all levels of facilities, such as public, school and even private spaces.

1.2.1 Different Type of Swimming Pools

- Public/private
- Indoor/outdoor/mixed type
- Sports/Gyms/Rehabilitation/Spas/Whirlpools/Hot tubs/ Hotels
- Built in-ground/ built above ground
- With bleachers/without bleachers

1.2.2 Use of Swimming Pools

Swimming pools are also used for events such as synchronized swimming, water polo, canoe polo and underwater sports such as underwater hockey, underwater rugby, fin swimming and sports diving as well as for teaching diving, lifesaving, and scuba diving techniques. They have also used for specialist tasks such as teaching water-ditching survival techniques for aircraft and submarine crews and astronaut training. Round-cornered, irregular swimming pools, such as the Nude Bowl, were drained of water and used for vertical skateboarding.

1.2.3 Size of Swimming Pools

Swimming pools have a lot of designs and shapes depending on type and use. The next Table 1.1 shows the variety of swimming pool's size according to the type of the pool.

Table 1.1: Swimming pool's size according to the type of pool. [2] [3]

Type	Dimensions			
	Length (m)	Width (m)	No. of lanes	Depth (m)
Learner pool**	10.00-20.00	7.00	2	0.60-0.90
Community pool 20m**	20.00	8.50	4	0.80-1.00/1.50
		10.50	5	
Community pool 25m**	25.00	8.50	4	0.90-1.50 min
		10.50	5	1.00-2.00 pref
		12.50	6	
Competition +	25.00*	13.00	6	1.00-1.80 min
Short course championship +	25.00*	17.00	8	1.80
Training pool	50.00*	10.00-17.00	4-8	1.00-1.80 min
ASA National Competition+	50.00*	19.00	8	1.00-1.80 min
		21.00		2.00 pref
FINA National Competition+	50*	21.00	8	1.35 min 2.00 pref

FINA International Competition+	50.00*	25.00	8	2.00 min
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ASA Amateur Swimming Association

FINA Federation Internationale de Natation (English: International Swimming Federation)

* For competition pools, an allowance should be made for automatic touchpads and for the finished dimensions between surfaces of the timing touchpads/ walls to be certified by an approved surveyor

** Provision of a movable floor allows the pool to use in multi-purpose community use.

+ Spectator and competitor seating provision appropriate to the level of competition should be discussed and agreed with the ASA/FINA

A more general classification of the size of the swimming facilities according to the total water surface (WS) of the swimming pools into the facilities:

- Category 1: Facilities with up to 300 m² WS
- Category 2: Facilities between 300 m² and 600 m² WS
- Category 3: Facilities with more than 600 m² WS

However, the total WS of a swimming pool plays an essential role in the energy use of a swimming facility.

1.3 Control of Ventilation System

At present the swimming pool are controlled by using empirical knowledge, it means, the pools controlled by hand regulations. Many of these hand regulations are very well-considered, but they are based on existing knowledge and experiences of operation instead of requirement analysis because there is not valid knowledge about how to obtain the optimized operations from modern simulation tools. It is no doubt that the control and regulation strategy is a powerful tool to reduce the energy consumption for ventilation and water treatment system. However, it is much difficult to set optimal regulation conditions because no suitable model can be used to simulate and compare different influencing factors.

The control of the ventilation system is complicated since it based on the empirical knowledge instead of the optimal requirement control. Not only should good indoor air quality is to be considered in swimming pools – primarily from air temperature and humidity, but also the pools, people, building, and energy consumption should consider. Here the water evaporation rate from pools is the essential parameter which influences the indoor climate and energy consumption. It is essential to keep the balance between the air and the water surface, and the water evaporation rate should reduce as much as possible.

1.4 Water Evaporation and Air Temperature

Reliable calculation methods of evaporation from swimming pools is needed for sizing the air conditioning system as well as for energy consumption calculations. No well-verified evaporation model is available at present. Underestimation of evaporation will lead to the selection of small air-conditioning equipment, resulting in excessive humidity that can cause discomfort to the occupant and damage to the building from mold growth and rot. On the contrary, an overestimation will result in the selection of oversized equipment with high cost, excessive energy consumption, and operating problems because of excessive cycling.

Relation between water evaporation, air temperature and air humidity at a still water surface and low air velocity in a swimming pool shows that an acceptable low water evaporation can obtain when keeping the air temperature 28 °C and water temperature 26°C, which is a starting point for dimensioning the ventilation system and choosing the water temperature.

Practical experiences of operation with ventilation show also that the balance between air and water surface is extremely sensitive due to a small change in air and water conditions. Also, the massive glass façade also increases the demand for indoor climate and ventilation system when the cold and condensation should reduce. When choosing reasonable operating conditions in swimming pools, moisture problems, as well as operational expenditure, should be controlled. The pool hall temperature should always be higher than the pool water temperature to minimize evaporation rates.

The higher the temperature differential between air and water, the lower the evaporation rate from the pool surface. However, to maintain a reasonable operating economy, the difference should not be more than 2-3°C [4].

1.4.1 Water Evaporation and Air Movement CFD Simulation

The CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) technology enables engineers to study fluid dynamics, and it is a tool for compressing the design and development cycle. Using CFD, a computational model can be built to study. When the fluid flow physics applied to this virtual prototype, the CFD software can simulate how it will perform under real-world conditions and output a prediction of the fluid dynamics. CFD is a sophisticated analysis technique; it predicts not only fluid flow behavior but also the heat and mass transfer. CFD analysis gives the ability to optimize design early, reducing the need for costly and time-consuming physical testing.

The boundary conditions collected from the measurement results including air temperature, water temperature, humidity and ventilation flow rate. The ventilation and water evaporation from pools mutually coupled, so this case can use in a CFD calculation model, where both water evaporation and air movement can be dealt with simultaneously. Therefore, the CFD can give different detailed information of air flow and humidity distribution in the room due to different water evaporation models, and a valid model for swimming pools will obtain.

1.5 Objective of The Thesis

- Maintain the design temperature and humidity to secure proper air quality within the pool hall.
- Calculated amount of fresh air into the pool hall, the desired relative humidity can maintain. This process has the potential to use a great deal of energy.
- Recover as much heat as possible from the exhaust air and to avoid changing air more than is necessary.
- Control of the local air temperature over pool, which the air temperature should be 2-3 °c higher than the water temperature in the pool, and partly limitation of the air velocity over pool surface. Higher regulation accuracy for inlet air temperature, good air mixing with uniform temperature and low air velocity should be demanded to fulfill the instruction's requirements.

1.6 Scope of The Thesis

The objective of the thesis is to provide incentives for integrating energy efficiency in the planned renovation by developing new energy saving solutions for ventilation and water treatment, and at the same time ensure the improvement of indoor climate and water quality.

The research work and development work will establish on measurements in existing swimming pools combined with calculations and analyses for a model swimming pool including indoor climate, working environment, water quality, as well as energy consumption. Furthermore, a complete economic estimation of installations and operation will create; as such a comprehensive study will often lead to further energy saving measures.

The result of the project will be used to set up a method of fault detection and diagnosis in existing public swimming pools including instructions and solutions for dimensioning of ventilation systems and water treatment facilities. The result will also be used both for new installations and renovations of existing pools.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The primary purpose of review of previous researchers is trying to improve the understanding of flow processes and turbulent flow characteristics enclosure space and to illustrate the development of the calculation methods in prediction of the indoor air environment. All that is help in determine the conditions flow which uses in a program of prediction to airflow pattern enclosure space. The previous experimental and numerical investigations of airflow characteristics enclosure spaces is presented in this chapter. That is trying to indicate the advances, findings, and conclusions.

Moreover, the literature review, not only aims to present the accomplishments of the various studies, but also compare the results of this thesis with those of the present papers and identify the less-studied areas that can investigate thoroughly.

2.2 Previous Researches

Abdelhakim Limane et al. [5]: Performed a simulation of the three-dimensional airflow with heat and mass transfer in a complex geometry indoor swimming pool shown in Figure 2.1 using the OpenFOAM software. The comparison of numerical results with experimental measurements of air velocity, temperature and humidity showed good agreement regardless of the turbulence model.

Two simulations carried out with winter and summer weather conditions. Their comparison showed a minimal effect on the internal environment which is manifested by a greater temperature stratification in winter. Furthermore, the effect of swimmers on the indoor atmosphere of the swimming pool evaluated and found to be of great importance. The main advantageous effect is the homogenization of the temperature and the specific humidity in the occupied area. On the other hand, its major adverse effect is the increase of the specific humidity in the air.

Figure 2.1: Pool mesh: (a) Section along the x-axis (b) Section along the y-axis [5]

The study showed that it is possible to successfully model this three-dimensional airflow with heat and mass transfer using the free software OpenFOAM. Thus, CFD studies of the conditions in large enclosed spaces with Heating, Ventilation, and Air-Conditioning (HVAC) can perform at low-cost. The numerical results obtained by the different RANS turbulence models are acceptable. However, the results obtained by the model k-e Launder & Sharma are the most satisfactory.

The mean significant findings of this study are the horizontal distributions of temperature and humidity are more uniform while their vertical gradients near the water surface are smaller. While, in the spectator stands, the temperature and humidity are not influenced by the activity of swimmers to any significant extent. The mean advantageous effect is the homogenization of the temperature and the specific humidity in the occupied area. On the other hand, its significant adverse effect is the increase of the specific humidity in the air.

Juan Luis et al. [6]: Presented a new methodology in which a CFD model is applied to estimate water evaporation rate in indoor swimming pools. The primary hypotheses of the model set the following boundary conditions at the air-water interface: air temperature equal to water temperature, water vapor concentration equal to saturation humidity of air at water temperature and free slip wall condition (no shear stress). The model experimentally validated by using data from three different test chambers and a real swimming pool.

The dependence of the error in the estimated values of evaporation rates on the different convection mechanisms studied regarding the dimensionless number Gr/Re^2 , which approximates the ratio of the buoyancy and inertial forces. Relative errors of the evaporation rate concerning experimental values are smaller for mixed convection conditions for which the numerical/experimental ratio is 1.01 ± 0.10 . The highest dispersion of errors found for conditions in which forced convection dominates.

Mathieu Lebonet al. [7]: Developed a numerical code, based on the zonal method to investigate the indoor airflow patterns and thermal comfort of their occupants (TCO) in indoor swimming pool. The numerical simulation validated against intensive field measurements. Carried out in the public indoor swimming pool shown in Figure 2.2 located at Bishop's University (Sherbrooke, Quebec, Canada), of the temperature, velocity, and relative humidity of the air as well as the surface temperature of the walls, ceiling, and floor. The developed code is then used to study the indoor flow patterns and to evaluate the TCO using three indexes: the humidex chart, the predicted mean vote (PMV), and the predicted percentage of dissatisfied (PPD). The results show a hot-humid causing uncomfortable atmosphere is prevailing in the occupied parts of the studied indoor swimming pool. The calculated airflow rates show that, due to the position of the ventilation inlets and outlets, most of the ventilation air circulates in the upper part of the building causing an insufficient air renewal in the occupied parts of the studied indoor swimming pool.

Figure 2.2: Photos of the investigated indoor swimming pool [7]

The results show that in these areas, an uncomfortable atmosphere for the occupants is prevailing. The corresponding values for the predicted percentage of dissatisfied (PPD) and predicted mean vote (PMV) indices confirm these conclusions, even though their calculations did not consider transient phenomena and evaporation. Furthermore, the evaluation of the air changes per hour (ACH) for the same zones shows a mixed result; some zones present an appropriate air renewal and others poorly ventilated or over ventilated.

Piotr Ciuman et al. [8]: Studied the effect of selecting the calculation formula of mass flux of moisture emitted from the pool shown in Figure 2.3, to improve numerical predictions of air parameters distribution in swimming pool. The numerical results of these parameters in the occupied zone validated by comparison with the measurements results executed at selected points of this area. The study showed that the best compliance of numerical prediction of air specific humidity and speed with the measurements results obtained with the use of VDI formula. The German standard VDI 2089 recommends the correlation, in which the evaporation factor introduced, $e = 5$ for calm pool surface.

Figure 2.3: Numerical model of half of the pool [8]

VDI 2089 Correlation:

The German calculation formula VDI-2089 states the required data for the design of indoor swimming pools, and the evaporation rate calculated as follows:

$$E = \frac{1}{3.6 \times 10^8} \varepsilon \times (P_w - P_a) \quad (2.1)$$

Where:

P_w is the saturated water vapor partial pressure at the water temperature

P_a is the water vapor partial pressure at the air temperature and humidity

e is empirical as:

$\varepsilon = 0.5$ for covered pool surfaces

$\varepsilon = 5$ for calm surface

$\varepsilon = 15$ for private swimming pool, not very occupied

$\varepsilon = 20$ for public swimming pool, normal activity

$\varepsilon = 28$ for leisure pool

$\varepsilon = 35$ for wave pool

Deming Liu et al. [9]: Investigated Interior Microclimate of Swimming Hall under Different Seat Arrangements, and Partition The results were symmetric seat arrangement is the optimal solution, Under competition Condition.

Piotr Ciuman et al. [10]: Evaluated the impact of the discretization grid refinement on the numerical calculations of the air parameters distribution in the actual school pool. The result showed that the tested discretization grids the range of analyzed parameters values were similar. However, introducing the refinement caused the change of their distributions in vertical and horizontal sections in the occupied zone.

The refinement of the discretization grid affected the range of air specific humidity values. The additional refinement above the water surface was especially important, as it actively affected the range of values and their distribution, not only in this region but the whole facility, and profoundly increased the accuracy of predicting specific humidity. Its predicted values are within the range of measuring error or slightly deviated from it.

Mirza M. Shah [11]: Studied the methods for calculation of evaporation from swimming pools and other water surfaces. The study presented and discussed the correlations for indoor occupied and unoccupied swimming pools. Also presented were methods for outdoor occupied and unoccupied swimming pools, hot-water pools such as nuclear fuel pools, decorative pools, tanks and vessels/containers.

Gian M. Revelet al. [12]: Developed a monitoring methodology that includes thermal comforting a smart metering system for sports facilities presented. The main result of this analysis confirms the possibility of using the PMV as a comfort index in sports facilities to evaluate the general comfort level and long-term benchmark, given that the increase of uncertainty concerning typical applications is in the order of ± 0.1 . Nevertheless, this study raises the need to improve the estimation of the metabolic rate.

Applied to a swimming pool is shown, where a lumped parameter model is used to simulate comfort and energy data throughout a whole year. The influence of the

measurement uncertainty on the comfort indicator evaluated with the data simulated confirming the applicability of the approach presented. It revealed that PMV/PPD indices could be used to evaluate the real thermal feeling experienced by pool users and to make an informed management decision for energy saving. Future work will focus on the extensive validation of the method in real scale pilots in the framework of the SportE2 project [13].

Piotr Koper et al. [14]: Suggested a way of assessing the conditions of thermal comfort existing in the occupied area, which would permit to compare explicitly various concepts of the air distribution in a ventilated room. Moreover, the suggest showed that the larger the share of the area in which the required criterion is satisfied, the more favorable would be an assessment of the given concept of the air distribution. The assessment of thermal comfort concerning the selected concept of the air distribution inside the room indicates that at the investigated height in the occupied zone in a considerable part of the area, requirements concerning temperature, relative humidity, and speed of air were satisfied. Lancaster-Castens-Ruge's sultriness curve exceeded only locally, and no draught felt. In a considerable part of this area, however, the conditions of thermal comfort could not be achieved, so that the values of PMV index would be realized, and thus also the values of PPD index, required in case of this category of rooms.

Figure 2.4: The hall of the swimming-pool
 a) The view of the actual object
 b) The numerical model, generated by CFX Ansys [14]

Figure 2.5: Discretization grid in the numerical model of the roofed swimming-pool
 a) In the entire space
 b) In the occupied zone around the pool [14]

Antonio D'Aquilio et al. [15] [16]: performed a simulation in early stages design to reduce the energy consumption that used for ensuring high comfort levels for both athletes and spectators and Predict of temperature and airflow patterns by providing natural instead of Mechanical Ventilation. A case study (Jiangmen Sports Center, Jiangmen, China) is used to test the developed process for a large indoor sports hall. It found that These measures highly depend on the shape, construction and ventilation openings, which mostly decided in the early design stages. This type of simulation in early design stages can lead to the higher future performance of buildings regarding indoor microclimate.

The study revealed that correlations between even simple design parameters lead to partially unexpected results that might not be directly foreseen by the designer.

Marco Arnesano et al. [17]: Dedicated measurement performance index is calculated to determine the location of the optimum sensor that provides the maximum accuracy with the minimum number of sensors to deployed. The application and validation of the tool in actual indoor swimming pool outlined that the measurement uncertainty due to the wrong location of the existing thermostat was higher than ± 0.5 °C (thermostat uncertainty datasheet) for the 42% of the period considered.

The description of the criteria adopted to design is the monitoring system concerning some sensors and location often omitted since it is based on experience and without the use of supporting tools that capture the real thermal characteristics of the environments. Thus, a dedicated methodology allowing the optimization of the sensor network to focus measurement accuracy, minimal number and location of sensors are needed.

The validation of the tool based on measured data. The best solution of sensors positioning coming from the simulation and measurements corresponds regarding location and measurement performance.

The analysis of measured data showed a bias due to the location of the existent thermostat with a mean value of 0.6 °C and 42% of working hours with a standard deviation, due to the sensor location, higher than sensor uncertainty. The new optimal sensors network decreased the bias to a mean value of 0.13 °C and only 1.5% of the lifetime.

Figure 2.6: General scheme of the indoor swimming pool in Fidia shown the location of the optimal sensor retrieved with simulated and measured datasets of temperature [17]

Mohamed Abo Elazm et al. [18]: Investigated the effect of air velocity, and evaporation rate on the indoor air quality in enclosed swimming pools hall (San-Stefano Grand Plaza swimming pool which located in Alexandria, Egypt) has been carried out using CFD modeling. It was found out from this study that the increase in the evaporation rate from the swimming pool surface is due to the lower temperature difference between air and water. The simulation results showed that the supply air velocity and temperature have a significant effect on the rate of evaporation, optimizing these two parameters could improve the indoor air quality inside enclosed swimming pools.

On the other hand, increasing the supply air velocity resulted in a reduction in relative humidity and temperature which enhance the indoor air quality within enclosed swimming pools.

Figure 2.7: Thermocouples located at different levels [18]

Figure 2.8: Proposed 2D model for the indoor swimming pool [18]

Baris Yuce et al. [19]: presented an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) approach to predict energy consumption and thermal comfort level (represented by Predicted Mean Vote (PMV)) of an indoor swimming pool. The proposed methodology has been used to predict the energy consumption and PMV value for an indoor swimming pool in the Fidia facility, located in Rome (Italy), a general overview of the Fidia pilot shown in Figure 2.9. The proposed approach had been utilizing for a use case scenario: “HVAC management and control using an intelligent system.” All input and output variables of ANN defined in this use case scenario. To train and test the ANN models, a MATLAB-Simulink based model has been utilized to generate the required data sets. Several ANN models tested, and the parameters tuning have been successfully carried out for the best performed ANN model. According to the results, Levenberg-Marquardt training algorithm-based ANN model has been found as best performed ANN model; then the parameter tuning was accomplished based on the determination of transfer functions and some process elements in hidden layers. For future work, the proposed ANN will be utilized as a cost function engine to develop intelligent energy and thermal comfort management system for this pilot.

Figure 2.9: General overview of the Fidia pilot [19]

Figure 2.10: The topology of the proposed ANN for the HVAC system of swimming pool [19]

Francesco Asdrubali [20]: Measured the water evaporation rate under controlled environmental conditions in designed swimming pool model shown in Figure 2.11. The measured parameters were water temperature, air temperature, relative humidity, and air velocity. The result was A new prediction model has therefore been proposed to evaluate the evaporation flow rate from indoor swimming pools. The model compared with some of the most widely known models found in the literature, and in particular, the Shah, Hannsen and Mathisen and Smith models, derived from measurements in real pools, and a good agreement found.

Figure 2.11: Experimental apparatus for water evaporation measurements [20]

Figure 2.12: Schematic design of the swimming pool model [20]

The experimental apparatus shown in Figure 2.12 for the tests is made up of:

- 1 Environmental test chamber:
Mazzali Climatest Model climatic chamber, dimensions $700\text{ mm} \times 660\text{ mm} \times 680\text{ mm}$, the chamber is equipped with two centrifugal fans to guarantee uniformity and with heating elements and a refrigerating machine to control air temperature
- 2 Precision balance:
Scalded model Bel Engineering Ultra Mark 4000, digital screen, range from 0 to 4 kg, accuracy $\pm 0.01\text{ g}$; operating temperature conditions between 0 and $40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, relative humidity between 20% and 85%, used to value evaporated mass.
- 3 External aluminum container:
dimensions are $300\text{ mm} \times 300\text{ mm} \times 95\text{ mm}$, internally insulated with polyurethane foam 50 mm thick, so that heat exchange occurs mainly through the free water surface.
- 4 Internal aluminum container:
dimensions $250\text{ mm} \times 150\text{ mm} \times 70\text{ mm}$, container capacity 2.5 liter
- 5 Temperature regulator (Gefran 2000).
- 6 Temperature probe:
PT100, Class A, Din 43760, precision $\pm 0.04\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, immersed in the water and connected to the regulator; for measuring water temperature.
- 7 Thermal resistor:
used to heat water inside the container.

- 8 Wooden box:
used to regulate air velocity inside the climatic chamber.
- 9 Air velocity probe:
hotwire type, model BSV 101, with compensation for operating temperature conditions between 0 and 40 °C and relative humidity between 10% and 95%; the instrument precision is ± 0.01 m/s in the range 0: 1 m/s; an externally controllable mechanical stick allows one to move the probe appropriately over the container surface.
- 10 Fluke 45-01 mode
digital multimeter, for five figures and double fluorescent display, for signal acquisition of air velocity.

Jing Liua et al. [21]: Perform A series of experiments have been carried out to study the characteristics of indoor temperature and moisture distributions using a free water surface within a test chamber shown in Figure 2.13. Some parameters such as air change rates, surrounding air temperature and humidity, water temperature and water surface area, were chosen to find their influences on simultaneous moisture and heat transfer. Then used a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) method to simulate the cases corresponding to the experiments cases.

Figure 2.13: The test chamber with the position of the measurement points (unit: mm) [21]

Based on the simulation and experiment results and discussions, the following conclusions are made:

- Moisture transfer rate is a function that in a linear relation with the vapor pressure gradient and air change rate.
- By comparing the measured and predicted results, it can found that heat transfer rate by a vapor is a value somewhere between latent heat and sensible heat.

- The heat and moisture transfer rate independence of water surface area, which mean this approach is available for other cases of water surfaces.
- The simulation results show that a higher water temperature normally decreases both heat and moisture rate, while the opposite situation occurs with higher air temperature, but their effects are different.
- Compared with other ways of heat transfer, it is shown that heat transfer due to moisture is in the majority of total heat loss, about 60%.

Mohammad Moghiman et al. [22]: Performed an experimental investigation of the water evaporation rate into the moving air currents of indoor swimming pools. A series of experimental measurements have been carried out in the test chamber shown in Figure 2.14 Based on experimental measurements. The measured evaporation rates have a strong dependence on air velocity (Re number) and Sherwood number. The comparison between water evaporation rates from the free water surface and the wetted surface shows that for low air velocities, evaporation rate from a wetted surface is higher than that of free water surface and for high air velocities, this is reversed.

Figure 2.14: Experimental test chamber and its essential features [22]

The water evaporation measurements were carried out in a test chamber with internal dimensions of $150 \times 100 \times 100$ cm. The evaporation pond of test chamber was 25 cm deep and had five electric heaters located at the bottom and on the walls to maintain water at elevated temperatures. All surfaces of the chamber and evaporation pond were insulated with 5 cm polystyrene panels to reduce heat loss.

The air and water temperatures measured by eight thermocouples located 1 cm under the water surface and at different points of the chamber space. The relative humidity measured by six measurement points. A simple sketch of the test chamber and its essential features presented in Figure 2.14. Data from water and air temperature and relative humidity recorded by a personal computer data acquisition system. All sensors calibrated before measurements.

The laboratory had a controlled air conditioning system to maintain the air at a constant temperature and relative humidity. The inlet air temperature of the test chamber was controlled to maintain at 45°C (based on conventional air conditioning systems).

The air of the chamber was exhausted to outside by a centrifugal fan. The fan acted as a draw-thru unit (induced fan arrangement) to reduce the turbulent effects of air current on evaporation rate. Testo-405 anemometer with an accuracy of 1% was used to measure the airflow rates through the chamber.

The water evaporation loss was measured using the method of Pauken. It determined by connecting the evaporation pool to a small pan that rested on a digital scale through a siphon. The accuracy of the scale was 0.1g. The water loss in the evaporation pool in proportion to the mass change in the small weighing pan. The proportional constant is determined by removing a measured mass of water from the water pool and recording the change in mass on the scale.

Based on the results, the following conclusions may be drawn:

- Regression analysis shows that the measured evaporation rates have strong dependence on air velocity (Re number) and Sherwood number.
- The best non-linear fit to measure data indicates a third order decreasing functional relationship between the exponent of vapor pressure difference and water evaporation rate.
- The comparison between water evaporation rates from free water surface and wetted surface shows that for low air velocities, evaporation rate from wetted surface is higher than that of free water surface and for high air velocities, this is reversed.

2.3 Summary of Selected Previous Work

Table 2.1: Summary of the selected previous

S.No	Author(s)	Type of flow	Numerical Algorithm & Turbulence model	Applications / Main findings	Grid type
1	Abdelhakim Limane et al. [5]	3-D model, steady state, incompressible and turbulent flow	OpenFOAM [23] software, Different RANS turbulence models ($K - \varepsilon$, $RNG K - \varepsilon$, $K - \varepsilon$ <i>Lauder Sharma</i> , $K - \omega$)	Simulation of the three-dimensional airflow with heat and mass transfer in an indoor swimming pool and study the effect of swimmers on the indoor atmosphere. The main finding was the horizontal distributions of temperature and humidity are more uniform when swimmers are active while their vertical gradients near the water surface are smaller. While, in the spectator stands, the temperature and humidity are not influenced by the activity of swimmers to any significant extent.	coarse mesh composed of 7,640,144 cells
2	Juan Luis et al. [6]	3-D model, steady state, incompressible and turbulent flow	ANSYS Fluent 17.1 [24], a CFD program	Present a new methodology in which a computational fluid dynamics model is applied to estimate water evaporation rate in indoor swimming pools	—

3	Mathieu Lebonet al. [7]	3-D model, steady state, incompressible and turbulent flow	TRNSYS software (version 17) [25]	Developing a numerical code, based on the zonal method to investigate the indoor airflow patterns and TCO in the indoor swimming pool	—
4	Piotr Ciuman et al. [8]	3-D model, steady state, non-isothermal	ANSYS CFX software, the SST turbulence model from EVM models group, used	Study the effect of select the calculation formula of mass flux of moisture emitted from the pool to improve numerical predictions of air parameters distribution in the original pool.	1010544 tetrahedral elements and 2015095 nods
5	Deming Liu et al. [9]	3-D model, steady state, incompressible and turbulent flow	Airpak, Indoor-zero Equation model as turbulence model	Study the Different Seat Arrangements, and Partition The results were symmetric seat arrangement is the optimal solution.	The unit was meter, and max size ratio were two, max sizes in (X, Y, Z) was (2, 5.55, 3.45)
6	Piotr Ciuman et al. [10]	3-D model, steady state, incompressible and turbulent flow	ANSYS CFX [26]	Evaluate the impact of the discretization grid refinement on the numerical calculations of the air parameters distribution in the actual school pool.	Variants of unstructured discretization grids
7	Mirza M. Shah [11]	---	---	Studied the methods for calculation of evaporation from swimming pools and other water surfaces. The study presented and discussed the correlations for indoor occupied and unoccupied swimming pools	---

8	Gian M. Revelet al. [12]	---	SportE ² [27]	Developed a monitoring methodology that includes thermal comforting a smart metering system for sports facilities presented. It revealed that PMV/PPD indices could be used to evaluate the real thermal feeling experienced by pool users and to make an informed management decision for energy saving.	---
9	Piotr Koper et al. [14]	Models of turbulence, among others so far most frequently used two-equation models k-ε and SST.	Used CFD code ,CFX ANSYS [26].	Suggested a way of assessing the conditions of thermal comfort existing in the occupied area, which would permit to compare explicitly various concepts of the air distribution in a ventilated room. The assessment of thermal comfort concerning the selected concept of the air distribution inside the room indicates that at the investigated height in the occupied zone in a considerable part of the area, requirements concerning temperature, relative humidity, and speed of air were satisfied. Lancaster-Castens-Ruge's sultriness curve exceeded only locally, and no draught felt. In a considerable part of this area	consisted of 1976857 mostly tetrahedral elements.
10	Antonio D'Aquilio et al. [15] [16]	3-D model, steady state,	The voxel grid is generated automatically using a customized Grasshopper	Performed a simulation in early stages design to reduce the energy consumption that used for ensuring high comfort levels for both athletes and spectators and Predict temperature and airflow patterns by	voxel grid

		incompressible and turbulent flow	component. The airflow simulation is performed by CONTAM software [28]	providing natural instead of Mechanical Ventilation. The study revealed that correlations between even simple design parameters lead to partially unexpected results that might not be directly foreseen by the designer.	
11	Marco Arnesano et al. [17]		SportE ² [27], Sensor Optimization Unit (SOU) tool	Determine the location of the optimum sensor that provides the maximum accuracy with the minimum number of sensors to be deployed. The analysis of measured data showed a bias due to the location of the existent thermostat with a mean value of 0.6 °C and 42% of working hours with a standard deviation, due to the sensor location, higher than sensor uncertainty. The new optimal sensors network decreased the bias to a mean value of 0.13 °C and only 1.5% of the lifetime.	---
13	Mohamed Abo Elazm et al. [18]	3-D model and 2-D model, steady state, incompressible and turbulent flows	Using 2-D and 3-D CFD simulation	Investigated the effect of air velocity, and evaporation rate on the indoor air quality in enclosed swimming pools hall. The simulation results showed that the supply air velocity and temperature have a significant effect on the rate of evaporation, optimizing these two parameters could improve the indoor air quality inside enclosed swimming pools.	a non-uniform grid made of 8500 cells.

14	Baris Yuce et al. [19]	---	MATLAB Simulink [29], Design Builder and Energy+ [30], SportE ²	presented an ANN approach to predict energy consumption and thermal comfort level represented by PMV of an indoor swimming pool. According to the results, Levenberg-Marquardt training algorithm-based ANN model has been found as best performed ANN model; then the parameter tuning was accomplished based on the determination of transfer functions and some process elements in hidden layers. For future work, the proposed ANN will be utilized as a cost function engine to develop intelligent energy and thermal comfort management system for this pilot.	---
15	Francesco Asdrubali [20]	---	Experimental	Measured the water evaporation rate under controlled environmental conditions in a designed swimming pool model. The result was A new prediction model has therefore been proposed to evaluate the evaporation flow rate from indoor swimming pools.	--
16	Jing Liua et al. [21]	Standard k-e model	The Japanese CFD software STREAM [31]	Perform A series of experiments have been carried out to study the characteristics of indoor temperature and moisture distributions using a free water surface within a test chamber. Then used a CFD method to simulate the cases corresponding to the experiments cases.	CFD grid points: 39(X) × 47(Y) × 39(Z) = 71,487

17	Mohammad Moghiman et al. [22]	---	Experimental	<p>Performed an experimental investigation of the water evaporation rate into the moving air currents of indoor swimming pools. Based on experimental measurements, the measured evaporation rates have a strong dependence on air velocity (Re number) and Sherwood number. The comparison between water evaporation rates from the free water surface and the wetted surface shows that for low air velocities, evaporation rate from a wetted surface is higher than that of free water surface and for high air velocities, this reversed.</p>	---
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Chapter 3

Validation and Verification

3.1 Introduction

The numerical model investigation, incorporated in the present study, is used to investigate the airflow pattern, temperature, relative humidity distributions and the thermal comfort prediction based on the PMV model and the PPD model inside a semi-Olympic pool located at Bishop's University in Sherbrooke (Quebec, Canada) shown as Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Inside a semi-Olympic pool located at Bishop's University in Sherbrooke [5]

This chapter aims to validate the results of ANSYS Fluent with previous experimental and numerical work of Abdelhakim Limane et al. [5]. The work of Abdelhakim Limane et al. used to validate the numerical results with the experimental results by simulations of the 3D airflow using OpenFOAM software. The Present comparisons between the numerical results using ANSYS Fluent Software to those previously published experimental and numerical results obtained by different researchers in the field using OpenFOAM software.

3.2 Swimming Pool Description

The present validate concerns a semi-Olympic pool located at Bishop's University in Sherbrooke (Quebec, Canada). The space considered consists of a large

enclosure with complex geometry, of roughly trapezoidal shape and dimensions of (34.5 m × 25 m × 8 m). The enclosure consists of the water basin area, and the spectator stands, the two major parts partially separated from each other as shown in Figure 3.3. It has two exterior partially subterranean walls (in contact with the external environment) located on the north and west sides and two interior walls located on the east and south sides.

(a)

(b)

**Figure 3.2: The real geometry:
a) South-east side
b) North-east side [5]**

The control of the air temperature in the pool is ensured exclusively by the HVAC system. The many inlets and outlets of the ventilation system create a complicated flow field. The water basin area: covered by a false ceiling with six horizontal segments at different heights Figure 3.3(a), dotted with three rows of air inlets on its inclined parts, each row with six air inlets (1.05 m × 0.19 m) introducing air at an angle of 30° from horizontal. The air outlets (1.20 m × 0.6 m) are all located at the top of one horizontal segment at the opposite side (north side) to the three rows of air inlets. The spectator

Figure 3.3 : Pool dimensions and position of ventilation inlets/outlets:
(a) Cross-section showing position of spectator stands
(b) Longitudinal section showing form of false ceiling (not to scale) [5]

stands: covered with a long false ceiling and including six air inlets ($0.3 \text{ m} \times 0.3 \text{ m}$) which introduce the air on three sides at an angle of 30° from the horizontal.

3.3 Grid Generation and Mesh Criteria

For the most part in numerical modeling, the procedure of mesh generation consumes most of the effort and time. It is the mesh resolution that determines how well is the numerical solution predicated at every computational segment (cell) in the domain of interest. The cell size and shape are normally controlled and represented the two fundamental classes upon the overall grid is set.

1- Structured Meshes:

A structured mesh is described by regular connectivity that can be expressed as a two or three-dimensional array. This limits the element choices to quadrilaterals in 2D or hexahedra in 3D. In a structured mesh, we could store the mesh connectivity in an $(n \times m)$ array. The regularity of the connectivity allows us to conserve space since neighborhood relationships are defined by the storage arrangement. Additional classification can be made upon whether the mesh is conformal or non-conformal grid is the case where cell faces are attached together with different node location at the interfacing plane.

2- Unstructured Meshes:

An unstructured mesh is characterized by irregular connectivity is not readily expressed as a two or three-dimensional array in computer memory. This allows

for any possible element that a solver might be able to utilize. Compared to structured meshes, the storage requirements for an unstructured mesh can be substantially larger since the neighborhood connectivity must be explicitly stored. As far as the current research is concerned, a numerical algorithm had been used to divide the selected geometries into cells. The numerical algorithm for constructing the mesh is based on solving a set of partial differential equations with an iterative procedure to determine placements of node (cell) locations inside the whole domain; the process that is called automatic mesh generation. Therefore, the grid generation is transformed into algebraic relations based on geometric relationships that output the location of all cells. The meshing algorithm is developed by the solver meshing software using tetrahedral mesh element where every single cell is attached to the same number of neighboring cells and every cell face share a single interface at each connecting face with the neighboring cells (conformal meshing).

In the present work the choice of meshing using tetrahedral structured mesh has much helped in reducing computational expenses in terms of the total number of cells bearing into consideration the crucial importance of cell flow alignment, aspect ratio, skewness.

The swimming pool hall model was discretized into almost 7,000,000 tetrahedral elements. According to the Equi Angle skew mesh quality type specification, more than 70% of the cells had a value less than or equal 0.25 (classified as good elements). The Equi Angle Skew parameter is a normalized measure of skewness. For mesh skewness the smoothness mechanism supplied by the solver is used to have a better meshing to make it easier to get a convergent case. The mesh was generated using ANSYS Meshing Application as a pre-processor. The swimming pool hall structure is built using the ANSYS SpaceClaim 3D Modeling Software. The constructed lines are joined to form the faces which are stitched together to form the computational volume.

3.3.1 Boundary Conditions:

ANSYS
R17.2

Figure 3.4: Isometric view of the swimming pool hall

Figure 3.5: Plan view of the swimming pool hall

Figure 3.6: Side view of the swimming pool hall

■ Swimming pool ■ Inlet grille ■ Outlet grille ■ Lighting unit

3.3.1.1 The Inlet Air Conditions

Table 3.1: Boundary conditions of the inlet 1.05 m × 0.19 m

Type	Velocity inlet	Hydraulic diameter	0.3217 m
Length	1.05 m	Temperature	35 °C
Width	0.19 m	Specific humidity	0.017839 Kg/kg
Velocity	3.5 m/s	Angle	30°
Length	0.2252 m	Component of flow direction	$X = -1$ $Y = 0$ $Z = -0.87$

The spectator stands: covered with a long false ceiling and including six air inlets (0.3 m × 0.3 m) shown as Figure 3.7, which introduce the air on three sides at an angle of 30° from the horizontal.

Figure 3.7: Inlet which introduces the air on three sides

Table 3.2: Boundary conditions of the inlet 30 cm × 30 cm

Inlet side	R	L	M
Area	33750 mm ²	33750 mm ²	22500 mm ²
Perimeter	812.132 mm	812.132 mm	724.264 mm
Hydraulic diameter	0.1662 m	0.1662 m	0.1242 m
Type	Velocity inlet		
Velocity	3.5 m/s		
Angle	30° from the horizontal.		
Component of flow direction	$X = 1$ $Y = 0$ $Z = -0.87$	$X = -1$ $Y = 0$ $Z = -0.87$	$X = 0$ $Y = 1$ $Z = -0.87$
Temperature	35°C		
Specific humidity	0.01784 Kg/kg		
Length scale	0.1163 m	0.1163 m	0.0869 m
No. inlet	6	6	6

3.3.1.2 The Outlet Air Conditions

Table 3.3: Boundary conditions of the outlet

Length	Width	Type	Hydraulic diameter	No. of outlet
1.2 m	0.60 m	Pressure outlet	0.8 m	6

3.3.1.3 The Lighting

The lights are treated as a warm surface supplying a uniform heat flux to the air estimated to be 2 W/m².

Table 3.4: Boundary conditions of the lighting unit

Length	Width	Type	Heat flux	No. of the lighting unit
1.2 m	0.60 m	Wall	2 W/m ²	32

3.3.1.4 The Walls

Table 3.5: Boundary conditions of the walls

Type	No. of wall	Conditions	Temperature	Location
Interior walls	2	summer	20 °C	east and south sides
		winter	20 °C	
Exterior walls	2	summer	25 °C	north and west sides
		winter	-20 °C	

3.3.1.5 The Pool

Table 3.6: Boundary conditions of the pool

Length	Width	Hydraulic diameter	Type	Temperature	Specific humidity Kg/kg	Length scale	Mass flux Kg/m ² .s
25 m	14 m	18 m	Mass flow inlet	29 °C	0.0257	12.6 m	2.97 × 10 ⁻⁵ [11]

3.3.2 Grid Independency Check

The grid independency check achieved through comparisons of the same case for different grid sizes of 3.5, 5.6, 6.9 and 10 Million. The comparison is made through line plot shown in Figure 3.8 below.

Figure 3.8: Line 1 configuration

3.3.2.1 Mesh Quality

Mesh quality recommendations by ANSYS low orthogonal quality or high skewness values are not recommended [32].

Table 3.7: Skewness mesh metrics spectrum [32]

Excellent	Very good	Good	Acceptable	bad	Unacceptable
0-0.25	0.25-0.50	0.50-0.80	0.80-0.94	0.95-0.97	0.98-1.00

Table 3.8: Orthogonal quality mesh metrics spectrum [32]

Unacceptable	bad	Acceptable	Good	Very good	Excellent
0-0.001	0.001-0.14	0.15-0.25	0.20-0.69	0.70-0.95	0.95-1.00

Table 3.9: Orthogonal quality and skewness values for grid sizes

Mesh Quality Metrics	Grid sizes			
	3.5 Million	5.6 Million	6.9 Million	10 Million
Orthogonal Qualit	0.34	0.37	0.36	0.39
Skewness	0.65	0.62	0.63	0.60

Depicting the effect of different mesh size, four cases have been carried out. Figure 3.9: Temperature profiles at line 1, Figure 3.10: Relative humidity profiles at line 1 and Figure 3.11: Velocity profiles at line 1 depict the temperature, Velocity, and relative humidity distribution along line 1. The results using the four meshes show that the difference is insignificant but, the computing time of the fine mesh is 2 times slower. Therefore, the 5.6 Million mesh used for all simulations.

Figure 3.9: Temperature profiles at line 1

Figure 3.10: Relative humidity profiles at line 1

Figure 3.11: Velocity profiles at line 1

3.4 Validation Work

The Present comparisons made between the numerical results using ANSYS Fluent Software to those previously published experimental and numerical results obtained by different researchers in the field using OpenFOAM software. By compare velocity and Relative Humidity profiles at four lines in X-axis shown in Figure 3.12, and the cartesian coordinates of the line 1,2,3 and 4 shown in Table 3.10.

Figure 3.12: Lines 1,2,3 and 4 configurations

Table 3.10: Cartesian coordinates of the lines 1,2,3 and 4

	1 st point			2 nd point			Note
	X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z	
Line 1	0	0.5	0.2	35	0.5	0.2	
Line 2	0	0.5	3.25	35	0.5	3.25	In the same plane with line 1
Line 3	0	20.5	0.2	35	20.5	0.2	
Line 4	0	20.5	3.25	35	20.5	3.25	In the same plane with line 3

Figure 3.13: Velocity profiles at line 1

Figure 3.14: Velocity profiles at line 2

Figure 3.15: Velocity profiles at line 3

Figure 3.16: Velocity profiles at line 4

Figure 3.17: Relative humidity profiles at line 1

Figure 3.18: Relative humidity profiles at line 2

Figure 3.19: Relative humidity profiles at line 3

Figure 3.20: Relative humidity profiles at line 4

Figure 3.21: Line 5,6,7,8,9 and 10 configurations

Table 3.11: Cartesian coordinates of the lines 5,6,7,8,9 and 10

	1 st point			2 nd point			Note
	X	Y	Z	X	Y	Z	
Line 5	0	0.5	0.45	35	0.5	0.45	Lines 5,6 and 7 located in the same plane
Line 6	0	0.5	1.5	35	0.5	1.5	
Line 7	0	0.5	2.55	35	0.5	2.55	
Line 8	0	20.5	0.45	35	20.5	0.45	Lines 8,9 and 10 located in the same plane
Line 9	0	20.5	1.5	35	20.5	1.5	
Line 10	0	20.5	2.55	35	20.5	2.55	

Figure 3.26: Temperature profiles at line 9

Figure 3.27: Temperature profiles at line 10

3.5 Summary

A numerical code simulating the velocity, temperature, and relative humidity distributions of the air as well as the surface temperature of the walls, ceiling, and floor in the public indoor swimming pool of Bishop's University (Sherbrooke, Quebec, Canada) developed and validated numerically

After comparison between the two alternative CFD softwares, ANSYS Fluent with OpenFoam the result shown a good agreement between the results of the two software, more simulation models implemented in next chapter, to improved ventilation system. All the geometries of the configurations in this next chapter created by SpaceClaim software.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

The 6 Configurations compared between each other to reach the best design for location inlet and outlet to achieve the thermal comfort for swimmer and spectator at lowest ACH recommended by ASHRAE [33] 6 ACH.

The focus of the study improves the thermal comfort in the occupied zone in the hall, that located in the area around the swimming pool and spectator stand area, therefore the grilles of the inlet located in this area at different height and shape.

Table 4.1: The description of the 6 configurations

Configuratio	Inlet					Outlet					Solution	
	Shape	Dimension	No. of unit	Location		Shape	Dimension	No. of unit	Location			
				Water pool area	Spectator stands				Water pool area	Spectator stands area		
1		1.20 m × 0.60 m	12	8 in the ceiling above the water pool	2 in each side of the north wall and south wall	CFD equations of fluent software had converged at 1×10^{-3}						
2					6 unit in the ceiling					4 in the ceiling		
3				26 unit in the 4 walls of the water pool area at 0.3 m height	6 unit in the ceiling							
4					6 unit in the fence at 0.3 height							
5		1.20 m × 0.60 m	12	8 in the ceiling above the water pool	4 in the ceiling		CFD equations of fluent software had converged at 1×10^{-3}					
6		14 " 0.35m	22	---	22 unit in the ceiling							
		1.80 m × 0.20 m	26	26 unit in the 4 walls of the water pool area at 3 m height	---							

4.1 Boundary Conditions

4.1.1 Position of Ventilation

4.1.1.1 Configuration 1

Figure 4.1: Isometric view of the swimming pool hall configuration 1

Figure 4.2: Plan view of the swimming pool hall configuration 1

Figure 4.3: South view of the swimming pool hall configuration 1

Figure 4.4: East view of the swimming pool hall configuration 1

Figure 4.5: West view of the swimming pool hall configuration 1

■ Swimming pool ■ Inlet grille ■ Outlet grille ■ Lighting unit

4.1.1.2 Configuration 2

Figure 4.6: 3D view of the swimming pool configuration 2

Figure 4.7: Plan view of the swimming pool configuration 2

Figure 4.8: South view of the swimming pool configuration 2

Figure 4.9: East view of the swimming pool configuration 2

Figure 4.10: West view of the swimming pool configuration 2

■ Swimming pool
 ■ Inlet grille
 ■ Outlet grille
 ■ Lighting unit

4.1.1.3 Configuration 3

Figure 4.11: 3D view of the swimming pool configuration 3

Figure 4.12: Plan view of the swimming pool configuration 3

Figure 4.13: South view of the swimming pool configuration 3

Figure 4.14: East view of the swimming pool configuration 3

Figure 4.15: West view of the swimming pool configuration 3

■ Swimming pool
 ■ Inlet grille
 ■ Outlet grille
 ■ Lighting unit

4.1.1.4 Configuration 4

Figure 4.16: 3D view of the swimming pool configuration 4

Figure 4.17: Plan view of the swimming pool configuration 4

Figure 4.18: South view of the swimming pool configuration 4

Figure 4.19: East view of the swimming pool configuration 4

Figure 4.20: West view of the swimming pool configuration 4

■ Swimming pool
 ■ Inlet grille
 ■ Outlet grille
 ■ Lighting unit

4.1.1.5 Configuration 5

Figure 4.21: 3D view of the swimming pool configuration 5

Figure 4.22: Plan view of the swimming pool configuration 5

Figure 4.23: South view of the swimming pool configuration 5

Figure 4.24: East view of the swimming pool configuration 5

Figure 4.25: West view of the swimming pool configuration 5

Swimming pool
 Inlet grille
 Outlet grille
 Lighting unit

4.1.1.6 Configuration 6

Figure 4.26: 3D view of the swimming pool configuration 6

Figure 4.27: Plan view of the swimming pool configuration 6

Figure 4.28: South view of the swimming pool configuration 6

Figure 4.29: East view of the swimming pool configuration 6

Figure 4.30: West view of the swimming pool configuration 6

■ Swimming pool
 ■ Inlet grille
 ■ Outlet grille
 ■ Lighting unit

4.1.2 The Inlet Air Conditions

4.1.2.1 Configurations 1, 2, 3 and 4

The inlet grilles in configurations 1,2,3 and 4 had the same size, shape and boundary conditions with a different position.

Table 4.2: Boundary conditions of the inlet 1.80 m×0.20 m

Type	Velocity inlet	Hydraulic diameter	0.36 m
Length × width	1.80 m × 0.20 m	Temperature	16 °C
No. of inlet	32	Specific humidity	0.00563 Kg/kg

Table 4.3: Calculation of velocity of the supply air according to ACH

ACH	Volume m^3	Volume flow rate			Inlet area m^2	Velocity m/s
		CFM	m^3/hr	m^3/s		
6	5764	20357	34586	10	0.36	0.83
8		27142	46115	13		1.11
10		33928	57643	16		1.39
12		40713	69172	19		1.67
14		47499	80701	22		1.95
16		54284	92229	26		2.22
18		61070	103758	29		2.50
20		67855	115286	32		2.78
22		74641	126815	35		3.06
24		81426	138344	38		3.34

4.1.2.2 Configuration 5

The configuration 5 had only circular inlet shape with the biggest standard size located at the ceiling as recommended by ASHRAE Handbook—HVAC Applications, [33].

Table 4.4: Boundary conditions of the circular inlet shape 14"

Type	Velocity inlet	Hydraulic diameter	14"-0.35 m
Diameter	14"-0.35 m	Temperature	16 °C
No. of inlet	64	Specific humidity	0.00563 Kg/kg

Table 4.5: Calculation of velocity of the supply air according to ACH

ACH	Volume m^3	Volume flow rate			Inlet area m^2	Velocity m/s
		CFM	m^3/hr	m^3/s		
6	5764	20357	34586	10	0.099	1.42
8		27142	46115	13		1.90
10		33928	57643	16		2.37
12		40713	69172	19		2.85
14		47499	80701	22		3.32
16		54284	92229	26		3.79
18		61070	103758	29		4.27
20		67855	115286	32		4.74
22		74641	126815	35		5.22
24		81426	138344	38		5.69

4.1.2.3 Configuration 6

The location and the shape of the inlet and the outlet in configuration 6 taken from comparing the other configurations together.

Table 4.6: Boundary conditions of the inlet 1.80 m×0.20 m

Type	Velocity inlet	Hydraulic diameter	0.36 m
Length × width	1.80 m × 0.20 m	Temperature	16 °C
No. of inlet	26	Specific humidity	0.00563 Kg/kg

Table 4.7: Calculation of velocity of the supply air according to ACH

ACH	Volume m^3	Volume Flow Rate			Inlet area m^2	Velocity m/s
		CFM	m^3/hr	m^3/s		
6	5376	18985	32256	9	0.36	0.96
8		25314	43009	12		1.28
10		31642	53761	15		1.60
12		37971	64513	18		1.91

Table 4.8: Boundary conditions of the circular inlet shape 14"

Type	Velocity inlet	Hydraulic diameter	14"
Diameter	14"	Temperature	16 °C
No. of inlet	22	Specific humidity	0.00563 Kg/kg

Table 4.9: Calculation of velocity of the supply air according to ACH

ACH	Volume m^3	Volume flow rate			Inlet area m^2	Velocity m/s
		CFM	m^3/hr	m^3/s		
6	388	1371	2330	0.65	0.099	0.30
8		1828	3106	0.86		0.39
10		2285	3883	1.08		0.49
12		2742	4659	1.29		0.59

4.1.3 The Outlet Air Conditions

The number of outlet unit and size were the same in all configurations, but the position was different.

Table 4.10: Boundary conditions of the outlet

Length	Width	Type	Hydraulic diameter	No. of outlet
1.2 m	0.60 m	Pressure outlet	0.8 m	12

4.1.4 The Lighting

The lights units treated as a hot face bringing a uniform heat flux to the atmosphere

Table 4.11: Boundary conditions of the lighting unit

Length	Width	Type	Heat flux	No. of the lighting unit
1.2 m	0.60 m	Wall	$2 W/m^2$	32

4.1.5 The Walls

Table 4.12: Boundary conditions of the walls

Type	No. of wall	Conditions	Temperature	Location
Interior walls	2	Summer	35 °C	East and south sides
Exterior walls	2	Summer	40 °C	North and west sides

4.1.6 The Pool

The evaporate rate of the water in the swimming pool calculated to the lowest air temperature, and the highest water temperature can be, Using larger of equations (4.1) and (4.2) [11].

$$E_0 = C\rho_w(\rho_r - \rho_w)^{\frac{1}{3}}(w_w - w_r) \quad (4.1)$$

$$E_0 = b(p_w - p_r) \quad (4.2)$$

Where:

$$C = 35$$

$$b = 0.00005$$

w = specific humidity of air, kg of moisture/kg of air

E_0 = rate of evaporation from unoccupied pools, kg/m²·h

p = partial pressure of water vapor in air, Pa

ρ = density of air, mass of dry air per unit volume of moist air, kg/m³

Subscripts

r = at room temperature and humidity

w = saturated at water surface temperature

Figure 4.31: Evaporation rate from unoccupied indoor swimming pools

Table 4.13: Boundary conditions of the pool

Type	Mass flow inlet	Temp. of water	30 °C
Width	14 m	Temp. of air	16 °C
Hydraulic diameter	18m	Length scale	12.5 m
Length	25 m	Mass flux	0.02421Kg / s [11]

4.2 Configurations Results

The simulated results of the 6 configurations were considered at three planes on X-axis and four planes on Y-axis.

4.2.1 Planes

4.2.1.1 YZ Planes

Figure 4.32: Plan view of the geometry shown the planes X- 1,2 and 3 locations on X-axis

Figure 4.33: Another view of the geometry shown the planes X- 1,2 and 3 locations on X-axis

Table 4.14: Location of the planes X at X axis

Color	Plane Name	Location at X axis	Notes
Red	Plane X-1	At X = 6 m	At the diving board
Green	Plane X-2	At X = 18 m	At the middle of the hall
Purple	Plane X-3	At X = 32 m	

4.2.1.2 XZ Planes

Figure 4.34: Plan view of the geometry shown the planes Y- 1,2,3 and 4 locations on Y-axis

Figure 4.35: Another view of the geometry shown the planes Y- 1,2,3 and 4 locations on Y-axis

Table 4.15: Location of the planes Y at Y axis

Color	Plane Name	Location at Y-axis	Notes
Blue	Plane Y-1	At Y = - 4 m	At the 2 nd level of the spectator seats
Light Blue	Plane Y-2	At Y = 2 m	
Red	Plane Y-3	At Y = 11 m	At the middle of the hall and the diving stand
Grey	Plane Y-4	At Y = 20 m	

4.2.2 Simulation Results of Air Velocity

The simulation results of air velocity compared at seven planes for all configurations within minimum air velocity (0 m/s) and maximum air velocity (1.48 m/s) as shown in Figure 4.36 to Figure 4.42.

Figure 4.36: Simulation result of air velocity at plane X-1

Figure 4.37: Simulation result of air velocity at plane X-2

Figure 4.38: Simulation result of air velocity at plane X-3

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

Figure 4.39: Simulation result of air velocity at plane Y-1

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

Figure 4.40: Simulation result of air velocity at plane Y-2

Figure 4.41: Simulation result of air velocity at plane Y-3

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

Figure 4.42: Simulation result of air velocity at plane Y-4

The air velocity in configuration 1 shown that increasing the air velocity at the sides of the spectator stand area due to the location of the outlet grilles, and the air distribution in the swimming pool area was better than spectator stand area

The velocity results in configuration 2 had the same result for configuration 1 in the swimming pool area, and better result in the spectator stand area due to the change of outlet grilles from the side wall to the ceiling.

The result in configuration 3 had the same result for configuration 2 in the spectator stand area because the same location of the inlet and outlet grilles, and it had terrible air distribution than configuration 1 and 2 due to the position of the inlet grilles at the 30 cm height.

Configuration 4 had the same air distribution for configuration 3 in the swimming pool area, and low air distribution result in the spectators stand area due to the low position of the inlet grilles at the fence

The configuration 5 results achieve air distribution condition of thermal comfort in spectator stand area and low air distribution for the rest of the hall due to the low-speed inlet of the air and the height of the hall, the air has low distribution nearest the floor and got better near the ceiling due to the location of the inlet and outlet grilles on the ceiling.

Air velocity has reached the desire condition of thermal comfort in configuration 6 , Therefore configuration 6 has the best air distribution from all configurations.

4.2.3 Simulation Results of Air Temperature

The simulation results of air temperature compared at seven planes for all configurations within a minimum air temperature (16 °C) and maximum air temperature (40 °C) as shown in Figure 4.43 to Figure 4.49.

Figure 4.43: Simulation result of air temperature at plane X-1

Figure 4.44: Simulation result of air temperature at plane X-2

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

Figure 4.45: Simulation result of air temperature at plane X-3

Figure 4.46: Simulation result of air temperature at plane Y-1

Figure 4.47: Simulation result of air temperature at plane Y-2

Figure 4.48: Simulation result of air temperature at plane Y-3

Figure 4.49: Simulation result of air temperature at plane Y-4

The air temperature in configuration 1 shown that increase the air temperature at the sides of the spectator stand area due to the location of the outlet grilles, and the air temperature distribution in the swimming pool area was better than spectator stand area

The air temperature results in configuration 2 had the same result for configuration 1 in the swimming pool area, and decreased in the spectator stand area due to the change of outlet grilles from the side wall to the ceiling.

The result in configuration 3 had the same result for configuration 2 in the spectator stand area because the same location of the inlet and outlet grilles, and it had terrible air temperature distribution than configuration 1 and 2 due to the position of the inlet grilles at the 30 cm height.

Configuration 4 had the same air temperature distribution for configuration 3 in the swimming pool area, and increase air temperature in the spectator stand area due to the low position of the inlet grilles at the fence and low air velocity distribution.

The configuration 5 results achieve air temperature distribution condition of thermal comfort in spectator stand area and high air temperature for the rest of the hall due to the low-speed inlet of the air and the height of the hall, the air temperature has decreased nearest the floor and increased near the ceiling due to the location of the inlet and outlet grilles on the ceiling.

Air temperature distribution has reached the desire condition of thermal comfort in Configuration 6. Therefore configuration 6 has the best air temperature distribution from all configurations

4.2.4 Simulation Results of Relative Humidity (RH%)

The simulation results of relative humidity compared at seven planes for all configurations within minimum relative humidity (17 RH%) and maximum relative humidity (50 RH%) as shown in Figure 4.50 to Figure 4.56.

Figure 4.50: Simulation result of relative humidity at plane X-1

Figure 4.51: Simulation result of relative humidity at plane X-2

Figure 4.52: Simulation result of relative humidity at plane X-3

Figure 4.53: Simulation result of relative humidity at plane Y-1

Figure 4.54: Simulation result of relative humidity at plane Y-2

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

Figure 4.55: Simulation result of relative humidity at plane Y-3

Figure 4.56: Simulation result of relative humidity at plane Y-4

The relative humidity in configuration 1 shown that increase the relative humidity at the sides of the spectator stand area due to the location of the outlet grilles, and the relative humidity distribution in the swimming pool area was better than spectator stand area

The relative humidity results in configuration 2 had the same result for configuration 1 in the swimming pool area, and better result in the spectator stand area duo to the change of outlet grilles from the side wall to the ceiling.

The result in configuration 3 had the same result for configuration 2 in the spectator stand area because the same location of the inlet and outlet grilles, and it had high relative humidity than configuration 1 and 2 due to the position of the inlet grilles at the 30 cm height.

Configuration 4 had the same relative humidity distribution for configuration 3 in the swimming pool area, and high result in the spectators stand area due to the low position of the inlet grilles at the fence

The configuration 5 results achieve relative humidity condition of thermal comfort in spectator stand area and high result for the rest of the hall due to the low-speed inlet of the air and the height of the hall, the relative humidity has increased nearest the floor and decreased near the ceiling due to the location of the inlet and outlet grilles on the ceiling.

Relative humidity has reached the desire condition of thermal comfort in Configuration 6. Therefore configuration 6 has the best air temperature distribution from all configurations

4.2.5 Simulation Results of PMV

The simulation results of PMV compared at seven planes for all configurations within minimum PMV (-0.87) and maximum PMV (4.37) as shown in Figure 4.57 to Figure 4.63.

Figure 4.57: Simulation result of PMV at plane X-1

Figure 4.58: Simulation result of PMV at plane X-2

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

-0.87 -0.09 0.70 1.49 2.27 3.06 3.84 4.37

PMV

Figure 4.59: Simulation result of PMV at plane X-3

Figure 4.60: Simulation result of PMV at plane Y-1

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

PMV

Figure 4.61: Simulation result of PMV at plane Y-2

Figure 4.62: Simulation result of PMV at plane Y-3

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

PMV

Figure 4.63: Simulation result of PMV at plane Y-4

The PMV in configuration 1 shown that decrease the PMV at the sides of the spectator stand area due to the location of the outlet grilles, and the air PMV in the swimming pool area was better than spectator stand area

The PMV result in configuration 2 had the same result for configuration 1 in the swimming pool area and better result in the spectator stand area due to the change of outlet grilles from the side wall to the ceiling.

The result in configuration 3 had the same result for configuration 2 in the spectator stand area because the same location of the inlet and outlet grilles, and it had high PMV than configuration 1 and 2 due to the position of the inlet grilles at the 30 cm height.

Configuration 4 had the same PMV for configuration 3 in swimming pool area, and high result in the spectator stand area due to the low position of the inlet grilles at the fence

The configuration 5 results shown low PMV result in spectator stand area and high result for the rest of the hall due to the low-speed inlet of the air and the height of the hall, the air had a low distribution nearest the floor and increased near the ceiling due to the location of the inlet and outlet grilles on the ceiling.

Configuration 6 shown a proper PMV result that reached -0.8 to 1 witch achieve thermal comfort condition, therefore configuration 6 has the best PMV from all configurations

4.2.6 Simulation Results of PPD

The simulation results of PPD compared at seven planes for all configurations within minimum PPD (5) and maximum PPD (100) as shown in Figure 4.64 to Figure 4.70.

Figure 4.64: Simulation result of PPD at plane X-1

Figure 4.65: Simulation result of PPD at plane X-2

Figure 4.66: Simulation result of PPD at plane X-3

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

Figure 4.67: Simulation result of PPD at plane Y-1

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

Figure 4.68: Simulation result of PPD at plane Y-2

Figure 4.69: Simulation result of PPD at plane Y-3

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

Configuration 4

Configuration 5

Configuration 6

Figure 4.70: Simulation result of PPD at plane Y-4

The PPD in configuration 1 shown that decrease the PPD at the sides of the spectator stand area due to the location of the outlet grilles, and the PPD in the swimming pool area was better than spectator stand area

The PPD result in configuration 2 had the same result for configuration 1 in the swimming pool area and better result in the spectator stand area due to the change of outlet grilles from the side wall to the ceiling.

The result in configuration 3 had the same result for configuration 2 in the spectator stand area because the same location of the inlet and outlet grilles, and it had higher PPD than configuration 1 and 2 due to the position of the inlet grilles at the 30 cm height.

Configuration 4 had the same PPD for configuration 3 in swimming pool area, and high result in the spectator stand area due to the low position of the inlet grilles at the fence

The configuration 5 results shown a low PPD result in spectator stand area and high PPD result for the rest of the hall due to the low-speed inlet of the air and the height of the hall, the air had a high PPD nearest the floor and got lower near the ceiling due to the location of the inlet and outlet grilles on the ceiling.

Configuration 6 shown a proper PPD range (5 to 10) at the location of for all the hall. Therefore configuration 6 has the best PPD from all configurations.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Recommendations for Future Work

5.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to present the conclusions drawn from the results of the configurations proposed, the present study investigated the flow regimes, temperature and relative humidity distributions inside an indoor swimming pool. The study carried out using CFD simulation using a commercial CFD package, namely ANSYS Fluent 17.2. The CFD modeling techniques solved the continuity, momentum, energy, and species transport equations in addition to k-epsilon model equations for turbulence closure. Mesh element sizes used in the present work exceeded 5.6 million mesh element which allowed better and meaningful predictions of the flow regimes.

5.2 Conclusions

- The validation results showed a good agreement between ANSYS Fluent 17.2 results and OpenFOAM software results.
- the results of the comparisons between configuration 5 and 2 revealed that the circular inlet in the ceiling at low-speed air supply shown better performance in spectator stand area than rectangle inlet.
- The results of the comparisons between configuration 5 and 2 shown that rectangle inlet in side walls in swimming pool area shown better performance than circular inlet at low-speed air supply due to the height of the hall.
- Low height of inlet grilles shown low thermal comfort results from the position the inlet grilles at 3m height by comparing configuration 1 and 2 with configuration 3 and 4.
- Configuration 6 is the best design for the swimming pool hall.
- ACH for the water pool area and spectator stand should be different due to the number of person per square meter as shown from configuration 6.

5.3 Recommendations for Future Work

Study:

- The design of configuration 6 at the different size of swimming pool hall.
- The change of ACH for the water pool area and spectator stand area.
- The dynamic change of evaporates rate of water vapor duo to the change of air temperature and the effect of the swimmers' activity.
- The effect of the change of ceiling shape to air distribution is to be investigated.
- The swimming pool hall with a maximum number of spectator and swimmers.

6 References

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Appendix A

Governing Equations

A.1 Introduction

CFD is a powerful tool for the analysis of fluid flows. It is a computer-based simulation technique providing an approximate two or three-dimensional solution to the equations governing fluid motion. The technique characterized by a division of the region in which flow is to be computed the computational domain, into a vast number of much smaller domains referred to as mesh or grid cells. Complex geometries and time-dependent flows readily handled. The solution consists of values of flow parameters of interest such as velocity or gas concentration, calculated at each of the grid cells. It provides a complete time-dependent picture of complex fluid flows.

CFD is a computer-based tool for simulating the behavior of system involving fluid flow, heat transfer and other related physical processes. It works by solving the equations for the conservation of mass, momentum, turbulence, and energy at every cell over a region of interest with prescribed (known) conditions on the boundary of the region. Commonly known as the Navier-Stokes equation, these equations are highly non-linear partial differential equations that describe the fundamental behavior of the fluid. Because these equations cannot solve in a closed form, this CFD software employs what are known as "differencing" techniques to derive approximate solutions to the equations throughout the geometry modeled. CFD makes use of computer simulation to obtain an approximate solution of the governing equations of fluid flow.

For the present study, CFD simulation for airflow inside the swimming pool hall, numerical techniques are used to model the airflow characteristics using continuity equation, momentum equations and energy equation.

A.2 Fluid Element for Conservation Laws

The present numerical analysis is used to solve the governing equations in the differential form. That means that a differential control volume in the continuum fluid considered to yield the analysis entirely. Figure A.1 represents the differential fluid element as well as its dimensions in the Cartesian coordinates.

The typical element has $\delta x, \delta y, \text{ and } \delta z$ sides in the $x, y, \text{ and } z$ direction respectively. These six faces are labelled $N, S, E, W, T, \text{ and } B$ that stands for the North, South, East, West, Top, and Bottom direction respectively.

Fluid properties typically stored in the center, node, of the control volume of fluid element namely (x, y, z) point.

Figure A.1: Fluid element for conservation laws

A.3 Governing Equations

A.3.1 Mass Conservation

To derive the mass conservation, we should write down the mass balance on the fluid element.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The rate of increase of mass} &= \text{The net rate of mass flow} \\ \text{in the fluid element} &\quad \text{into the fluid element} \end{aligned}$$

The rate of increase of mass inside the fluid element is

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \delta x \delta y \delta z) = \frac{\delta \rho}{\delta t} \delta x \delta y \delta z \quad (\text{A.6})$$

The net rate of flow of mass into the fluid element is equal to the difference between the rate of mass flowing into the fluid element and the rate of mass flowing out of the fluid element.

$$-\frac{\delta(\rho u)}{\delta x} \delta x \delta y \delta z - \frac{\delta(\rho v)}{\delta y} \delta x \delta y \delta z - \frac{\delta(\rho w)}{\delta z} \delta x \delta y \delta z \quad (\text{A.7})$$

By equating the rate of increase of mass inside the fluid element in equation (A.6) to the net rate of flow of mass into a fluid element in equation (A.7), we get the following equation.

$$\frac{\delta \rho}{\delta t} \delta x \delta y \delta z + \frac{\delta(\rho u)}{\delta x} \delta x \delta y \delta z + \frac{\delta(\rho v)}{\delta y} \delta x \delta y \delta z + \frac{\delta(\rho w)}{\delta z} \delta x \delta y \delta z = 0 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Dividing the equation (A.8) by $\delta x \delta y \delta z$ we get,

$$\frac{\delta \rho}{\delta t} + \left[\frac{\delta(\rho u)}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(\rho v)}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(\rho w)}{\delta z} \right] = 0 \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Equation (A.9) is the **unsteady compressible flow**, three-dimensional mass conservation equation (continuity equation) at a point in a compressible fluid.

Using the notation $(V \cdot \nabla \rho)$ to the terms in the brackets in equation (A.9) we obtain the following form

$$\frac{\delta \rho}{\delta t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho V) = 0 \quad (\text{A.10})$$

For *incompressible flow*, the density ρ is constant, so the equation (A.10) becomes

$$(\nabla \cdot V) = 0 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

A.3.2 Momentum Equation

The resultant force acting on a fluid mass is equal to the time rate of change of the linear momentum of the mass which merely is Newton's Second Law applied to a mass dm .

Where the mass element $dm = \rho dx dy dz$

The rate of increase of fluid particle momentum = sum of forces exerted on the fluid particle

For the above equation, the rate of increase of momentum in the x, y, z direction is defined as $\rho \frac{Du}{Dt}$, $\rho \frac{Dv}{Dt}$, $\rho \frac{Dw}{Dt}$ respectively.

Two forces are acting on a fluid particle:

First. Surface force.

- Pressure force.
- Viscous force (shear forces – normal forces).

The surface forces are consisting of pressure P and viscous force τ , the viscous stresses notation τ_{ij} is used usually to indicate the direction of the viscous stresses. Suffices τ_{ij} indicates that the viscous stress is in the j -direction and perpendicular to i -direction.

Figure A.2: Stress components on the six faces of the fluid element.

The x-components forces regarding pressure P and stress components τ_{xx} , τ_{yx} and τ_{zx} on the faces T, B, N, S, E and W are represented in the Figure A2. The force magnitude result from surface stress is the product of the stress by the area.

The total surfaces forces per unit volume in the x-direction is the summation of the components on the six faces.

$$\frac{\delta(-P + \tau_{xx})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta\tau_{yx}}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta\tau_{zx}}{\delta z} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Without considering the body forces in further detail, their overall effect can include by defining a source S_{Mx} of x-momentum per unit volume and per unit time.

The x-component of the momentum equation sets the rate of change of x-momentum equal to the total forces in the x-direction in addition to the rate of increase due to term S_{Mx} source.

$$\rho \frac{Du}{Dt} = \frac{\delta(-P + \tau_{xx})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta\tau_{yx}}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta\tau_{zx}}{\delta z} + S_{Mx} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

y-momentum equation:

$$\rho \frac{Dv}{Dt} = \frac{\delta\tau_{xy}}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(-P + \tau_{yy})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta\tau_{zy}}{\delta z} + S_{My} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

z-momentum equation:

$$\rho \frac{Dw}{Dt} = \frac{\delta\tau_{xz}}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta\tau_{yz}}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(-P + \tau_{zz})}{\delta z} + S_{Mz} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Second. Body forces – Gravity forces:

The body force explicitly accounted is the source term, for example, the body force per unit volume due to gravity is equivalent to $S_{Mx} = 0$, $S_{My} = 0$ and $S_{Mz} = -\rho g$.

The viscous stresses are related to the molecular viscosity of the fluid μ (according to the Stoke's law: stress = $\mu \times$ rate of strain) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xx} &= 2\mu \frac{\delta u}{\delta x} \\ \tau_{yy} &= 2\mu \frac{\delta v}{\delta y} \\ \tau_{zz} &= 2\mu \frac{\delta w}{\delta z} \\ \tau_{xy} = \tau_{yx} &= \mu \left[\frac{\delta u}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta v}{\delta x} \right] \\ \tau_{yz} = \tau_{zy} &= \mu \left[\frac{\delta v}{\delta z} + \frac{\delta w}{\delta y} \right] \\ \tau_{xz} = \tau_{zx} &= \mu \left[\frac{\delta u}{\delta z} + \frac{\delta w}{\delta x} \right] \end{aligned}$$

A.3.3 Energy Equation

The energy equation primarily derived from the first law of thermodynamics applied to the control volume defined in Figure A.1. It can be defined that:

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Rate of increase} \\ \text{of energy} \\ \text{of a fluid particle} \end{array} = \begin{array}{l} \text{Net rate of} \\ \text{heat added} \\ \text{to fluid particle} \end{array} + \begin{array}{l} \text{Net rate of} \\ \text{work done} \\ \text{on the fluid particle.} \end{array}$$

A.3.4 The Energy of A Fluid-Particle

The rate of increase of energy of a fluid particle can be given by,

$$\rho \frac{DE}{Dt} \quad (\text{A.16})$$

E is the total energy of a fluid particle (control volume) defined as:

$$E = h - \frac{P}{\rho} + \frac{v^2}{2} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

For ideal gases, the sensible enthalpy, h , is defined as:

$$h = \sum_j Y_j h_j \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Moreover, for incompressible flows as:

$$h = \sum_j Y_j h_j + \frac{p}{\rho} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Where Y_j is the mass fraction of species j and $h_j = \int_{T_{ref}}^T c_{p,j} dT$, where T_{ref} is 298.15 K.

A.3.4.1 Heat Added to Fluid-Particle

The flux vector q has three components q_x, q_y and q_z . the net rate of heat addition to the fluid particle can be given by the summation of the differences between the rates of heat input and heat loss across each to opposite faces.

The net rate of heat transfer in the X, Y, and Z-directions.

$$-\frac{\delta q_x}{\delta x} \delta x \delta y \delta z \quad , \quad -\frac{\delta q_y}{\delta y} \delta x \delta y \delta z \quad , \quad -\frac{\delta q_z}{\delta z} \delta x \delta y \delta z \quad (\text{A.20})$$

The total heat added to the fluid particle per unit volume due to heat transfer across the boundaries is,

$$-\frac{\delta q_x}{\delta x} - \frac{\delta q_y}{\delta y} - \frac{\delta q_z}{\delta z} = -div \, q \quad (\text{A.21})$$

The heat flux depends on the conductivity k and the local temperature gradient. Therefore, the heat flux in the x, y and z directions are,

$$q_x = -k \frac{\delta T}{\delta x} \quad , \quad q_y = -k \frac{\delta T}{\delta y} \quad , \quad q_z = -k \frac{\delta T}{\delta z} \quad (\text{A.22})$$

That can write in the vector notation as,

$$\begin{aligned} q &= -k \text{ grad}T \\ -\text{div} q &= \text{div}(k \text{ grad}T) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

A.3.4.2 Work Done on Fluid-Particle

The rate of work done by surface forces on a fluid particle given by the product of the force and the velocity component in the direction of the force. The net rate of work done by surface force in the x-direction can summarize in,

$$\left[\frac{\delta[u(-P + \tau_{xx})]}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(u\tau_{yx})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(u\tau_{zx})}{\delta z} \right] \delta x \delta y \delta z \quad (\text{A.24})$$

The rate of work done on a fluid particle by surface stress in the y-direction

$$\left[\frac{\delta(v\tau_{xy})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta[v(-P + \tau_{yy})]}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(v\tau_{zy})}{\delta z} \right] \delta x \delta y \delta z \quad (\text{A.25})$$

The rate of work done on a fluid particle by surface stress in the z-direction

$$\left[\frac{\delta(w\tau_{xz})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(w\tau_{yz})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta[w(-P + \tau_{zz})]}{\delta z} \right] \delta x \delta y \delta z \quad (\text{A.26})$$

The term containing pressure can write as,

$$-\frac{\delta(Up)}{\delta x} - \frac{\delta(vp)}{\delta y} - \frac{\delta(wp)}{\delta z} = -\text{div}(pu) \quad (\text{A.27})$$

The total rate of work done by surface forces on a fluid particle per unit volume can be given by

$$\begin{aligned} &-\text{div}(pu) + \frac{\delta(u\tau_{xx})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(u\tau_{yx})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(u\tau_{zx})}{\delta z} + \dots \\ &-\text{div}(pv) + \frac{\delta(v\tau_{xy})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(v\tau_{yy})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(v\tau_{zy})}{\delta z} + \dots \\ &-\text{div}(pw) + \frac{\delta(w\tau_{xz})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(w\tau_{yz})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(w\tau_{zz})}{\delta z} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.28})$$

Thus, from equating the sum of the net rate of work done on the fluid particle and the net rate of heat added to the fluid particle and the rate of increase of energy due to source SE to rate of change of energy of fluid particle we get the energy equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \frac{DE}{Dt} &= -\text{div}(pu) + \left[\frac{\delta(u\tau_{xx})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(u\tau_{yx})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(u\tau_{zx})}{\delta z} + \frac{\delta(v\tau_{xy})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(v\tau_{yy})}{\delta y} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\delta(v\tau_{zy})}{\delta z} + \frac{\delta(w\tau_{xz})}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta(w\tau_{yz})}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta(w\tau_{zz})}{\delta z} \right] + \dots \quad (\text{A.28}) \\ &\quad + \text{div}(k \text{ grad}T) + S_E \end{aligned}$$

A.3.5 Species Transport Equations

The solution of the conservation equations for chemical species present in the domain of the CFD model, the CFD code should predict the local mass fraction of each species Y_i in each control volume. That could be done by solving the convection-diffusion equation for the species i . This conservation equation takes the following general form:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho Y_i) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{v} Y_i) = -\nabla \cdot \vec{J}_i + R_i + S_i \quad (\text{A.29})$$

Where the term R_i refer to the net rate of production of species i by chemical reaction, and S_i is the rate of creation by addition from the dispersed phase or other sources like injections. Equation 4.29 is solved for $N - 1$ species where N is the total number of fluid phase chemical species present in the system. Since the mass fraction of the species must sum to unity, the N^{th} mass fraction is determined as one minus the sum of the $N - 1$ solved mass fractions. To minimize numerical error, the N^{th} species should be selected as that species with the overall largest mass fraction.

A.3.5.1 Mass Diffusion in Laminar Flows

In Equation 4.29, \vec{J}_i is the diffusion flux of species i , which arises due to concentration gradients. The dilute approximation is used in our modelling technique, under which the diffusion flux can be written as:

$$\vec{J}_i = -\rho D_{i,m} \nabla Y_i \quad (\text{A.30})$$

Where:

$D_{i,m}$ is the mass of diffusion coefficient for species i in the mixture.

For specific laminar flows, the dilute approximation may not be acceptable, and full multi-component diffusion is required. In such cases, the Maxwell-Stefan equations should use instead.

A.3.5.2 Mass Diffusion in Turbulent Flows

For turbulent flows, the mass diffusion is calculated using the following form:

$$\vec{J}_i = -\left(\rho D_{i,m} + \frac{\mu_t}{Sc_t}\right) \nabla Y_i \quad (\text{A.31})$$

Where:

Sc_t is the turbulent Schmidt number. The turbulent Schmidt number is set by default to 0.7; however, it can be calculated from the following equation:

$$Sc_t = \frac{\mu_t}{\rho D_t} \quad (\text{A.32})$$

Where:

μ_t is the turbulent viscosity and D_t is the turbulent diffusivity.

A.3.5.3 Treatment of Species Transport in the Energy Equation

The species transport included in the energy equation due to diffusive transport of enthalpy. This enthalpy transport has a significant effect on the enthalpy field and should not neglect. When the Lewis number (Le_i) for any species is far from unity, neglecting this term can lead to significant errors. The Lewis number is defined as:

$$Le_i = \frac{k}{\rho c_p D_{i,m}} \quad (\text{A.33})$$

Where:

k is the thermal conductivity.

A.3.6 Turbulence and its Modeling

Fluctuating velocity fields characterize turbulent flows. These fluctuations mix transported quantities such as momentum, energy, and species concentration, and cause the transported quantities to fluctuate as well. Since these fluctuations can be of small-scale and high frequency, they are too computationally expensive to simulate directly in practical engineering calculations. Instead, the instantaneous (exact) governing equations can be time averaged, ensemble-averaged, or otherwise manipulated to remove the small scales, resulting in a modified set of equations that are computationally less expensive to solve. However, the modified equations contain additional unknown variables, and turbulence models are needed to determine these variables regarding known quantities

A.3.6.1 Reynolds Averaging Equation

Reynolds suggests that any turbulent quantity $\phi(t)$ can be described as two components steady mean value $\bar{\phi}$ and fluctuating component $\phi'(t)$, Figure A.3 shows the typical behavior of velocity and any quantity at a point in the turbulent flow.

Figure A.3: Typical velocity measurement in turbulent flow

By applying the Reynolds decomposition on the velocity components and the pressure, then the flow properties can be defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}u &= U + u' \\v &= V + v' \\w &= W + w' \\p &= P + p'\end{aligned}$$

The mean flow property defined as the average time value of the property $\phi(t)$,

$$\phi = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_0^{\Delta t} \phi(t) dt \quad (\text{A.34})$$

The time average of the fluctuating component,

$$\overline{\phi'} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_0^{\Delta t} \phi'(t) dt \quad (\text{A.35})$$

Information regarding the fluctuating component of the flow property can obtain from the root mean square of the fluctuation:

$$\phi_{rms} = \sqrt{\overline{(\phi')^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_0^{\Delta t} (\phi')^2 dt} \quad (\text{A.36})$$

The continuity and Navier-Stokes Equations for incompressible flow with constant viscosity are;

$$\text{div } u = 0 \quad (\text{A.37})$$

$$\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} + \text{div}(uu) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta x} + \nu \text{div grad } u \quad (\text{A.38.a})$$

$$\frac{\delta v}{\delta t} + \text{div}(vu) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta y} + \nu \text{div grad } v \quad (\text{A.38.b})$$

$$\frac{\delta w}{\delta t} + \text{div}(wu) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta z} + \nu \text{div grad } w \quad (\text{A.38.c})$$

By applying time average rules on these equations,

$$\text{div } U = 0 \quad (\text{A.39})$$

$$\frac{\delta U}{\delta t} + \text{div}(UU) + \text{div}(\overline{u'u'}) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta x} + \nu \text{div grad } U \quad (\text{A.40.a})$$

$$\frac{\delta V}{\delta t} + \text{div}(VU) + \text{div}(\overline{v'u'}) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta y} + \nu \text{div grad } V \quad (\text{A.40.b})$$

$$\frac{\delta W}{\delta t} + \text{div}(WU) + \text{div}(\overline{w'u'}) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta z} + \nu \text{div grad } W \quad (\text{A.40.c})$$

The term in three equations (A.40.a-c) contains the product of fluctuating velocities and represent convective momentum due to velocity fluctuation replace with turbulent stress on the mean velocity component U, V and W ;

$$\frac{\delta U}{\delta t} + \text{div}(UU) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta x} + v \text{div grad } U + \left[-\frac{\overline{\delta u'^2}}{\delta x} - \frac{\overline{\delta u'v'}}{\delta y} - \frac{\overline{\delta u'w'}}{\delta z} \right] \quad (\text{A.41.a})$$

$$\frac{\delta V}{\delta t} + \text{div}(VU) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta y} + v \text{div grad } V + \left[-\frac{\overline{\delta u'v'}}{\delta x} - \frac{\overline{\delta v'^2}}{\delta y} - \frac{\overline{\delta v'w'}}{\delta z} \right] \quad (\text{A.41.b})$$

$$\frac{\delta W}{\delta t} + \text{div}(WU) = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\delta p}{\delta z} + v \text{div grad } W + \left[-\frac{\overline{\delta u'w'}}{\delta x} - \frac{\overline{\delta v'w'}}{\delta y} - \frac{\overline{\delta w'^2}}{\delta z} \right] \quad (\text{A.41.c})$$

The equations (A.41.a-c) can be given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta \rho U}{\delta t} + \frac{\delta \rho U^2}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta \rho UV}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta \rho UW}{\delta z} = -\frac{\delta p}{\delta x} + \left[\frac{\delta \tau_{xx}}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta \tau_{yx}}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta \tau_{zx}}{\delta z} \right] + \dots \\ + \left[-\frac{\overline{\delta \rho u'^2}}{\delta x} - \frac{\overline{\delta \rho u'v'}}{\delta y} - \frac{\overline{\delta \rho u'w'}}{\delta z} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.42.a})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta \rho V}{\delta t} + \frac{\delta \rho UV}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta \rho V^2}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta \rho VW}{\delta z} = -\frac{\delta p}{\delta y} + \left[\frac{\delta \tau_{xy}}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta \tau_{yy}}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta \tau_{zy}}{\delta z} \right] + \dots \\ + \left[-\frac{\overline{\delta \rho u'v'}}{\delta x} - \frac{\overline{\delta \rho v'^2}}{\delta y} - \frac{\overline{\delta \rho v'w'}}{\delta z} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.42.b})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta \rho W}{\delta t} + \frac{\delta \rho UW}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta \rho VW}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta \rho W^2}{\delta z} = -\frac{\delta p}{\delta z} + \left[\frac{\delta \tau_{xz}}{\delta x} + \frac{\delta \tau_{yz}}{\delta y} + \frac{\delta \tau_{zz}}{\delta z} \right] + \dots \\ + \left[-\frac{\overline{\delta \rho u'w'}}{\delta x} - \frac{\overline{\delta \rho v'w'}}{\delta y} - \frac{\overline{\delta \rho w'^2}}{\delta z} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.42.c})$$

The equations (A.41.a-c) are called the Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes equations (RANS), and the six new terms which bracketed in these equations called Reynolds stresses, as they represent the turbulent shear and normal stresses. In turbulent flow the normal stresses $-\overline{\rho u'^2}$, $-\overline{\rho v'^2}$ and $-\overline{\rho w'^2}$ are always non-zero as they contain squared velocities and the shear stresses $-\overline{\rho u'v'}$, $-\overline{\rho u'w'}$ and $-\overline{\rho v'w'}$ are associated with correlation between different velocities components, also the shear stress terms are non-zero as they contain correlated components.

Before going through turbulence modeling, we must define some terminologies associated with turbulence process, the kinetic energy of turbulence k :

$$k = \frac{1}{2} (\overline{u'^2} + \overline{v'^2} + \overline{w'^2}) \quad (\text{A.43})$$

Moreover, the turbulence intensity T_i is related to kinetic energy and the reference mean flow velocity as;

$$T_i = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}k}{U_{ref}} \quad (\text{A.44})$$

The turbulence stresses are found to increase as the mean flow rate of deformation increases, proposed by Bossinesq in 1877 that Reynolds stresses could be linked to the mean rates of deformation.

$$\tau_{ij} = -\overline{\rho u'_i u'_j} = \mu_t \left(\frac{\delta U_i}{\delta x_j} + \frac{\delta U_j}{\delta x_i} \right) \quad (\text{A.45})$$

$$\nu_t = \mu_t / \rho \quad (\text{A.46})$$

Where:

- μ_t is turbulent viscosity (dimension *pa.s*),
- ν_t is a kinematics turbulent viscosity (dimension m^2/s),
- the notation *i, j for i and j = 1* corresponds to x-direction and for *i and j = 2* corresponds to y-direction and for *i and j = 3* corresponds to z-direction.

The turbulent viscosity is used to close the momentum equations. We can use a similar assumption for the turbulent fluctuation terms that appear in the scalar transport equations. For a scalar property $\phi(t) = \Phi + \phi'(t)$:

$$-\overline{\rho \dot{u}_i \phi} = \Gamma_t \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x_i} \quad (\text{A.47})$$

Here Γ_t is the turbulent diffusivity. The turbulent diffusivity is calculated from the turbulent viscosity, using a model constant called the turbulent Schmidt number (Prandtl number) σ_t :

$$\sigma_t = \frac{\mu_t}{\Gamma_t} \quad (\text{A.48})$$

Experiments have shown that the turbulent Schmidt number is nearly constant with typical values between 0.7 and 1.

A.3.6.2 Turbulence Models

There is a variety of turbulence models available in the used commercial CFD package namely:

- Spalart-Allmaras model
- $k - \varepsilon$ models
 - Standard $k - \varepsilon$ model
 - Renormalization-group (RNG) $k - \varepsilon$ model
 - Realizable $k - \varepsilon$ model
- $k - \omega$ models
 - Standard $k - \omega$ model
 - Shear-stress transport (SST) $k - \omega$ model
- Reynolds stress model (RSM)

- Large eddy simulation (LES) model

A.3.6.3 The Standard k - ε Model

The standard $k - \varepsilon$ model is a semi-empirical model based on model transport equations for the turbulence kinetic energy (k) and its dissipation rate (ε). The model transport equation for k shown in equation 3.49 below derived from the exact equation, while the model transport equation for ε shown in equation 4.50 was obtained using physical reasoning and bears little resemblance to its mathematically counterpart. In the derivation of the $k - \varepsilon$ model, it assumed that the flow is fully turbulent, and the effects of molecular viscosity are negligible. The standard $k - \varepsilon$ model is, therefore, valid only for fully turbulent flows.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho k u_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_k + G_b - \rho \varepsilon - Y_M + S_k \quad (\text{A.49})$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \varepsilon) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho \varepsilon u_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} \right] + C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} (G_k + C_{3\varepsilon} G_b) - C_{2\varepsilon} \rho \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} + S_\varepsilon \quad (\text{A.50})$$

In these equations, G_k represents the generation of turbulence kinetic energy due to the mean velocity gradients. G_b is the generation of turbulence kinetic energy due to buoyancy. Y_M represents the contribution of the fluctuating dilatation in compressible turbulence to the overall dissipation rate. $C_{1\varepsilon}$, $C_{2\varepsilon}$, and $C_{3\varepsilon}$ are the $k - \varepsilon$ model constants. σ_k and σ_ε are the turbulent Prandtl numbers for k and ε , respectively. S_k and S_ε are user-defined source terms.

The turbulent (or eddy) viscosity, μ_t , is computed by combining k and ε as follows:

$$\mu_t = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon} \quad (\text{A.51})$$

Where: C_μ is a constant.

The model constants have the following default values:

$$C_{1\varepsilon} = 1.44, C_{2\varepsilon} = 1.92, C_\mu = 0.09, \sigma_k = 1.0, \sigma_\varepsilon = 1.3$$

These default values have been determined from experiments with air and water for fundamental turbulent shear flows including homogeneous shear flows and decaying isotropic grid turbulence. They have been found to work well for a wide range of wall-bounded and free shear flows.

The term G_k , representing the production of turbulence kinetic energy, can be easily modeled from the exact equation for the transport of k , this term may define as

$$G_k = -\overline{\rho u_i u_j} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \quad (\text{A.52})$$

To evaluate G_k in a manner consistent with the Boussinesq hypothesis,

$$G_k = \mu_t S^2 \quad (\text{A.53})$$

Where S is the modulus of the mean rate-of-strain tensor, defined as

$$S \equiv \sqrt{2S_{ij}S_{ij}} \quad (\text{A.54})$$

A.3.6.4 The RNG k-ε Model

k-ε equations derived from the application of a rigorous statistical technique (Renormalization Group Method) to the instantaneous Navier-Stokes equations.

Similar in form to the standard k-ε equations but includes:

- additional term in ε an equation that improves analysis of rapidly strained flows
- the effect of swirl on turbulence
- an analytical formula for turbulent Prandtl number
- the differential formula for effective viscosity

Improved predictions for:

- high streamline curvature and strain rate
- transitional flows
- wall heat and mass transfer

Transport Equations for the Standard k- ε model the turbulent kinetic energy, k , and its rate of dissipation, ϵ , are obtained from the following transport equations:

$$\underbrace{\rho U_i \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_i}}_{\text{Convection}} = \underbrace{\mu_t S^2}_{\text{Generation}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\alpha_k \mu_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_i} \right)}_{\text{Diffusion}} - \underbrace{\rho \epsilon}_{\text{Dissipation}} \quad (\text{A.55})$$

and

$$\underbrace{\rho U_i \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x_i}}_{\text{Convection}} = \underbrace{C_{\epsilon 1} \left(\frac{\epsilon}{k} \right) \mu_t S^2}_{\text{Generation}} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\alpha_{\epsilon} \mu_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x_i} \right)}_{\text{Diffusion}} - \underbrace{C_{\epsilon 2} \rho \left(\frac{\epsilon^2}{k} \right)}_{\text{Destruction}} - \underbrace{R}_{\substack{\text{Additional term} \\ \text{related to mean strain} \\ \text{\& turbulence quantities}}} \quad (\text{A.56})$$

Where

$$S \equiv \sqrt{2S_{ij}S_{ij}}, \quad S_{ij} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} \right)$$

$$R = \frac{C_{\mu} \rho \eta^3 (1 - \eta/\eta_0) \epsilon^2}{1 + \beta \eta^3} \frac{1}{k}$$

where $\eta \equiv Sk/\epsilon$, $\eta_0 = 4.38$, $\beta = 0.012$.

A.3.6.5 The Realizable k-ε Model

In addition to the standard and RNG-based k-ε models described in previous Sections, there is another model called realizable k-ε model. The term "realizable" means that the model satisfies certain mathematical constraints on the normal stresses, consistent with the physics of turbulent flows.

- Shares the same turbulent kinetic energy equation as Standard k-ε
- Superior performance for flows involving:
 - Planar and round jets
 - Boundary layers under strong adverse pressure gradients, separation
 - Rotation, recirculation
 - Strong streamline curvature
- Distinctions from Standard k-ε model:
 - Alternative formulation for turbulent viscosity

where

$$\mu_t \equiv \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon} \quad (\text{A.57})$$

is now variable

$$C_\mu = \frac{1}{A_o + A_s \frac{U^* k}{\varepsilon}} \quad (\text{A.58})$$

(A_o , A_s , and U^* are functions of velocity gradients)

- Ensures positivity of normal stresses; $\overline{u_i^2} \geq 0$
- Ensures Schwarz's inequality; $(\overline{u_i u_j})^2 \leq \overline{u_i^2} \overline{u_j^2}$

The new transport equation for dissipation rate, ε :

$$\rho \frac{D\varepsilon}{Dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} \right] + \rho c_1 S \varepsilon - \rho c_2 \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k + \sqrt{\nu \varepsilon}} + c_{\varepsilon 1} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} c_{\varepsilon 3} G_b \quad (\text{A.59})$$

Where G_b is the generation of turbulent kinetic energy due to buoyancy

Table A.1: Two equations $k - \varepsilon$ Models

Model	Main	Favourable applications
Standard $k - \varepsilon$ Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is considered the simplest complete model of turbulence. • Two separate transport equations allow the turbulent velocity and length scales to be independently determined. • It is the most reliable for practical engineering flow calculations. • It is a semi-empirical model, and the derivation of the model equations relies on phenomenological considerations and empiricism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust, computationally economical, and reasonably accurate for a wide range of turbulent flows. • Industrial flow and heat transfer simulations
RNG $k - \varepsilon$ Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was derived using a precise statistical technique. • It is similar in form to the standard $k - \varepsilon$ model, but it has been refined to include an additional term in its ε equation that significantly improves the accuracy for rapidly strained flows. • RNG theory provides an analytical formula for turbulent Prandtl numbers, while the standard $k - \varepsilon$ model uses user-specified, constant values. • Provides an analytically-derived differential formula for effective viscosity that accounts for low-Reynolds-number effects only if there is an appropriate treatment of the near-wall region. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The effect of swirl on turbulence included in the RNG model which leads to enhancing the accuracy for swirling flows. • The RNG $k - \varepsilon$ model is more accurate and reliable for a more extensive class of flows than the standard $k - \varepsilon$ model.

Model	Main	Favourable applications
Realizable <i>k</i> - ϵ Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It contains a new formulation for the turbulent viscosity and has a new transport equation for the dissipation rate, ϵ, derived from an exact equation for the transport of the mean-square vorticity fluctuation. • It called “realizable” as it satisfies certain mathematical constraints on the Reynolds stresses, consistent with the physics of turbulent flows. • One limitation of the realizable <i>k</i> - ϵ model is that it produces non-physical turbulent viscosities in situations when the computational domain contains both rotating and stationary fluid zones. • Recent validations for the realizable and RNG <i>k</i> - ϵ models in separated flows and flows with complex secondary flow features have shown that the realizable model provides the best performance of all the <i>k</i> - ϵ model versions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More accurate in the predictions of the spreading rate of both planar and round jets. • Provide superior performance for flows involving rotation, boundary layers under strong adverse pressure gradients, separation, and recirculation.

A.3.7 Buoyancy Effects on Turbulence in The k-ε Models

The generation of turbulence due to buoyancy is given by

$$G_b = \beta g_i \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \quad (\text{A.60})$$

Where: Pr_t is the turbulent Prandtl number for energy. For the standard and realizable $k - \varepsilon$ models, the default value of Pr_t is 0.85. The coefficient of thermal expansion β is defined as

$$\beta = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \right) \quad (\text{A.61})$$

الملخص

يلعب تصميم نظام تكييف الهواء داخل حمام سباحة مغطى دوراً حاسماً في توفير الراحة الحرارية والهواء النقي، وهدف هذا البحث هو دراسة تأثير تدفق الهواء على الحرارة ونقل الكتلة من خلال دراسة السرعة ودرجة الحرارة وتوزيع الرطوبة داخل قاعة حمام السباحة التي يشغلها كثير من الجماهير والسباحين.

أجريت الدراسة باستخدام الحسابات الديناميكية للموائع (CFD) باستخدام برنامج ANSYS Fluent 17.2، ولقد تم حل معادلات حفظ الكتلة و كمية الحركة و طاقة الجزيئات وكذلك تم استخدام نموذج k-epsilon لوصف السريان المضطرب. وعدد نقاط الشبكة الحسابية المستخدمة يزيد عن 5.6 مليون نقطة مما يتيح تنبؤ أفضل لنهج سريان الهواء.

تم دراسة حمام سباحة شبه أولمبي يقع في جامعة بيشوب في شيربروك (كيبك ، كندا) و تم استخدام برنامج SpaceClaim 3D لتصميم ستة حالات مختلفة ، حيث تضمن الدراسة تأثير موقع وعدد فتحات دخول و خروج الهواء عند أقل ACH (معدل تغير الهواء في الساعة) التي أوصت بها الجمعية الأمريكية لمهندسي التبريد والتدفئة وتكييف الهواء (ASHRAE) و التي تم تقييم و المقارنة بين القيم المستنتجة عن طريق Fanger's model .

تحسين الراحة الحرارية للمنطقة حول حمام السباحة و كذلك منطقة وقوف الجماهير الشاغل جزء رئيسي لهذه الدراسة ولتحقيق الظروف الملائمة في هذه الاماكن تم توزيع فتحات دخول الهواء في هذه المنطقة بارتفاعات وأشكال مختلفة.

كانت مخارج الهواء في الحالة الاولى في منتصف السقف في منطقة حمام السباحة وفي الجدران الجانبية لمنصة وقوف الجماهير ، كما كانت مداخل الهواء على ارتفاع 3 أمتار من الأرضية في الجدران الجانبية للحمام السباحة وفي الجدار الخلفي لمنطقة وقوف الجماهير ، في الحالة الثانية تقع مخارج الهواء في السقف في منطقة وقوف الجماهير و ذلك لدراسة تأثير تغيير موقع مخارج الهواء . اما الحالة الثالثة فتم فيها تغيير مداخل الهواء لتكون على ارتفاع 30 سم من الارض في منطقة حمام السباحة . وفي الحالة الرابعة تم تغيير مداخل الهواء في منطقة وقوف الجماهير لتكون في السور الامامي على ارتفاع 30 سم ، في حالة الخامسة تم تغيير شكل مداخل الهواء و استخدمت مداخل دائرية في السقف كما اوصت بها الجمعية الأمريكية لمهندسي التبريد والتدفئة وتكييف الهواء (ASHRAE)، في الحالة السادسة تم دراسة مديج من افضل النتائج المستنتجة من الحالات السابقة لتحقيق الراحة الحرارية المناسبة لحمام السباحة موضع الدراسة .

تم مقارنة النتائج بين برنامجي ANSYS Fluent 17.2 و OpenFOAM و ذلك للتحقيق من صحة نتائج برنامج ANSYS Fluent 17.2 المستخدم في الرسالة .

و كشفت نتائج الدراسة ان المدخل الدائري أظهر أداء أفضل من مدخل المستطيل في منطقة وقوف الجماهير و ذلك عند استخدام سرعات منخفضة ، كما أظهرت ان مدخل المستطيل أظهر أداء أفضل من مدخل الدائري في منطقة حمام السباحة .

و أخيراً معدل تغير الهواء في لساعة في منطقة حمام السباحة و منطقة وقوف الجماهير يجب ان يكون مختلف بسبب اختلاف عدد الأشخاص لكل متر مربع.

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شارع الملك فيصل - الجيزة - مصر

2016 / 10 / 1

2019 / /

هندسة القوى الميكانيكية

ماجستير العلوم

مهندس:

تاريخ الميلاد:

الجنسية:

البريد الإلكتروني:

التليفون:

عنوان:

تاريخ التسجيل:

تاريخ المنح:

القسم:

الدرجة:

المشرفون:

- أ . د / سامى مراد مرقص
- د / محمد علي إبراهيم
- مدرس بقسم هندسة الميكاترونيات
- كلية الهندسة ، جامعة 6 أكتوبر
- د / طاهر محمد ابوضيف

المتحنون:

- أ . د / محمد فائق عبد ربه
- أستاذ بقسم هندسة القوى الميكانيكية
- كلية الهندسة بشبرا - جامعة بنها
- أ . د / محمود أحمد فؤاد
- أ . د / سامى مراد مرقص

(المتحن الخارجي)

(المتحن الداخلي)

(المشرف الرئيسي)

عنوان الرسالة:

دراسة خصائص تدفق الهواء و الراحة الحرارية داخل حمام سباحة مغطى

الكلمات الدالة: حمام سباحة مغطى ، المباني الرياضية ، ديناميكا الموائع الحسابية ، تهوية ، معدل التبخر ، الظروف الحرارية والرطوبة ، الراحة الحرارية

ملخص الرسالة:

يلعب تصميم نظام تكييف الهواء في قاعة حمام السباحة الداخلية دورا حاسما في توفير الراحة الحرارية وبيئة النظافة. يمكن لهذه الدراسة تحسين وتطوير التصميم المعماري لضمان تحقيق الهدف الأمثل للهدف السابق. يهدف هذا البحث إلى دراسة تأثير تدفق ستارة الهواء على خصائص الحرارة والكتلة عن طريق حساب السرعة ودرجة الحرارة وتوزيع الرطوبة داخل حمام السباحة.

دراسة خصائص تدفق الهواء و الراحة الحرارية
داخل حمام سباحة مغطى

إعداد

المهندس / أحمد محمد حنفى محمود

رسالة مقدمة إلى كلية الهندسة – جامعة القاهرة
كجزء من متطلبات الحصول على درجة
ماجستير العلوم
في
هندسة القوى الميكانيكية

يعتمد من لجنة الممتحنين:

المشرف الرئيسى

الاستاذ الدكتور: سامى مراد مرقص

الممتحن الداخلى

الاستاذ الدكتور: محمود أحمد فؤاد

الممتحن الخارجى

الاستاذ الدكتور: محمد فائق عبد ربه

أستاذ بقسم هندسة القوى الميكانيكية
كلية الهندسة بشبرا - جامعة بنها

كلية الهندسة - جامعة القاهرة
الجيزة - جمهورية مصر العربية
2019

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تحت اشراف

أ.د. / سامى مراد مرقص

.....
الأستاذ بقسم هندسة القوى الميكانيكية
كلية الهندسة ، جامعة القاهرة

د. / ظاهر محمد ابوضيف

د. / محمد علي إبراهيم

.....
المدرس بقسم هندسة القوى الميكانيكية
كلية الهندسة ، جامعة القاهرة

.....
المدرس بقسم هندسة الميكاترونيات
كلية الهندسة ، جامعة 6 أكتوبر

كلية الهندسة - جامعة القاهرة
الجيزة - جمهورية مصر العربية
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